

Deliverable D3.4

Publication of Prize Winners in Cycle II (2024)

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1. Deliverable Scope

Contribution to project objectives

The publication of winners of the second cycle of the European Union Prize for Citizen Science in 2023 significantly contributes to the broader objectives of IMPETUS.

Publishing the winners showcases Europe's role as a global leader in citizen science. By recognizing and highlighting outstanding achievements in citizen science, the publication promotes Europe's contributions to the field and emphasises its leadership position. This aligns with the objective of IMPETUS to showcase Europe's role in citizen science.

The publication of winners also promotes and advocates for citizen engagement with science and research within the European Research Area. By highlighting the successful projects and their impact, the publication encourages greater participation and involvement of citizens in scientific activities. This supports the objective of the IMPETUS project to promote citizen engagement with science and research.

Furthermore, the publication of winners increases the visibility and dissemination of the European Union Prize for Citizen Science. By widely spreading information about the winners, the publication raises awareness about the prize and its objectives. This helps to attract more participation and submissions in future rounds of the Prize.

Relationship to other work packages

The publication of winners of the second cycle of the European Union Prize for Citizen Science in 2024 directly relates to the WP6 Dissemination & Communication. Several aspects of the project's communication objectives are supported by the publication of winners.

The publication of the winners contributes to the efforts of WP6 in making the ongoing work, aims and output of all work packages within IMPETUS more accessible to the public through various means such as publications, digital platforms, and press coverage of the prize winners. IMPETUS' objective to actively encourage public awareness, participation, and appreciation of citizen science initiatives is supported through showcasing the outstanding and inspiring practices currently undertaken in citizen science by the awarded projects.

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2. Overview of submission and selection process

Submissions overview

Submissions to the second cycle of the Prize were accepted from January 10 to March 11, 2024. In addition to extensive outreach through both the Ars Electronica and the IMPETUS communication channels on social media and newsletters to encourage submissions. A total of 967 projects were contacted directly with the encouragement to submit to the open call. The support of the European Research Executive Agency (REA) in spreading the open call by also promoting it on REA's communication channels was invaluable and greatly appreciated.

As in the first year, submissions were received through the Prize submission database hosted by Ars Electronica and cross-submissions from STARTS Prize and Prix Ars Electronica were possible. In 2024, the database was slightly updated to better match the IMPETUS data schema, making the collected data easier to integrate with other activities carried out by the project.

288 initiatives and projects were submitted to the Open Call for the second *European Union Prize for Citizen Science*, linking communities from across 61 countries – Spain and Great Britain were particularly well represented. Fifty percent of the submitting applicants were female, 45 percent male and 5 percent gender diverse.

The total number of submission to the European Union Prize for Citizen Science in 2024 was 288, from 49 countries. After the eligibility and admissibility checks the total numbers was 269. The second cycle had a total of 33 project that reapplied from the first cycle of the call.

The analysis of these submissions showed that the top countries for the second cycle of the call on the top ten were: Multinational/REA, Multinational/International, Germany, Spain, Italy, United Kingdom, France, Netherlands, Austria and Romania.

The list of countries for the final 30 winners selection: Multinational / REA (6), Multinational / INT (1), Germany (2), Greece (2), Hungary (1), Iceland (1), Italy(2) Latvia (1) Luxemburg (1), Netherlands (1), Serbia (1), Slovakia (1), Slovenia (1), Spain (4), Türkiye (1) and United Kingdom (4).

Gender distribution among the winners on 2024 (the data was taken from the person responsible for submitting the project to the Ars Electronica database): Female: 18 - Male: 11 - Rather not say: 1

Last year was the first call for the Accelerator. From the side of the European Union Prize for Citizen Science we saw that a few projects submitted to this year prize open call. In the final winner's selection 5 out of 30 came out from the Accelerator program. Honorary Mentions: Sicily's Indigenous Cyber Tracker, Obstetric Coevolution, Domestic Heat Comfort for Energy Poverty and Climate Adaptation, CITIZENS FOR SDG 15.1, and SeaPacs won the Diversity & Collaboration award.

Selection process

The first step in the selection process was the eligibility check. Ars Electronica team members checked all submissions to ensure they met the eligibility criteria. All eligible projects then moved on to the pre-selection phase.

During the pre-evaluation phase from March 17 to April 22, we involved an additional 5 pre-jury members (mainly part of Citizen Science panel of IMPETUS): Enza Lissandrello, Dr. Susanne Hecker, Maria Leão, Ana Macedo and Sofia Morazzo. They were part of the pre-evaluation phase together with the 5 main jury members that came to Linz for the final selection. During the pre-evaluation phase, each submission was reviewed by one pre-jury and one main jury member according to the award criteria. All submissions that passed the threshold of receiving a minimum of 20/30 points in both evaluations went on to be discussed in the main jury meeting.

The final jury selection was done in person in Linz from April 25 to 28, 2024, by the jury, consisting of; Fermín Serrano Sanz (ES), Luciana Marques (BR), Snežana Smederevac (RS), Mairéad Hurley (IE), Sofie Burgos-Thorsen (DK). All projects that had passed the pre-evaluation phase were discussed and analysed in detail by the jury members, until the final decision on the Award winners and Honorary Mentions was reached unanimously.

Winners' announcement

The *European Union Prize for Citizen Science - Grand Prize*, endowed with 60,000 euros, was awarded to the initiative *INCREASE: Intelligent Collections of Food-Legume Genetic Resources for European Agrofood Systems INCREASE Citizen Science Experiment (CSE)* from Italy, respectively a pan-European consortium and international cooperations. The *European Union Prize for Citizen Science - Diversity & Collaboration Award*, worth 20,000 euros, was awarded to *SeaPaCS: Participatory Citizen Science against Marine*

Pollution from Italy, and the European Union Prize for Citizen Science - Digital Communities Award, also worth 20,000 euros, was awarded to CoAct for Mental Health from Spain, respectively a pan-European consortium and international cooperations.

The jury also selected 27 Honorary Mentions of projects taking place across Europe. All winners, as well as the jury statements justifying their selection, are included in this document.

The winners were published on the [European Union Prize for Citizen website](#) and in the [IMPETUS website](#) on June 12, 2024. The [winners announcement was hosted by the European Research Executive Agency](#) (livestreamed June 12, 2024 at 11:15 am CEST in English) and also streamed to the [European Open Science Forum as a satellite event](#). A press release was published both by Ars Electronica and REA. Extensive social media communication on the channels of REA, IMPETUS and Ars Electronica accompanied the announcement.

Through the fruitful collaboration with REA in organising the announcement, its impact and the reach to international press could be significantly improved and recognition for prize winners by a wider audience could be achieved.

3. Next steps for the winners

The 30 winners selected by the jury of the second cycle of the European Union Prize for Citizen Science were contacted by the team of Ars Electronica and asked to provide project descriptions, biographies, credits and images for their awarded initiatives.

These texts were then edited by the Ars Electronica team, and uploaded to the prize website and published on the [European Union Prize for Citizen website](#) and on the [IMPETUS website](#) on June 12, 2024 at 11:15 am CEST to coincide with the [winners announcement hosted by the European Research Executive Agency](#), which was livestreamed to the public in English and a press release covered by Ars Electronica. The winners' pages for the European Union Prize for Citizen Science 2024 will be pushed to the [Ars Electronica Archive](#) next year (the winners from the 2023 cycle will be added to the Archive in the upcoming months as well). The prize winners were also shared widely on the IMPETUS, Ars Electronica, and the REA social media channels.

Members of the jury were also requested to co-write a joint statement about the European Union Prize for Citizen Science 2024 and a short statement on why each project was awarded. These statements from the jury were published online with the details of each [winning project](#) (check on "read more" to go directly to the individual winner's pages for more information).

Additionally, the jury statement, project descriptions of the three main prize winners, and a list of all Honorary Mentions will be included in the printed Prix Ars Electronica catalogue 2024 (to be published by Hatje Cantz), which also includes all winners of the Prix Ars Electronica and the STARTS Prizes. The book will be launched at the Ars Electronica Festival in September 2024. This will coincide with a Citizen Science exhibition at the Festival that will showcase selected projects. This exhibition will be shown in the part of the Festival venue that is freely accessible to the public (without ticket). Through this presentation at Ars Electronica, the winning projects are expected to reach an audience of +70,000 people.

4. Jury of the European Union Prize for Citizen Science 2024

The European Union's Citizen Science Prize makes a statement. It honours, presents and supports outstanding projects whose social and political impact advances the further development of a pluralistic, inclusive and sustainable society in Europe. The jury of the European Union Prize for Citizen Science 2024 was selected to ensure a diversity of expertise and backgrounds to ensure the selection of outstanding projects was pluralistic and inclusive across scientific disciplines and approaches to citizen science.

To increase the diversity of evaluation perspectives and to lighten the workload of jury members during the pre-evaluation phase, an additional five people were engaged to join the pre-jury. During the pre-evaluation phase, each eligible submission was reviewed by one jury member and one pre-jury member.

The 2024 jury members

Image 1. The jury of the European Union Prize for Citizen Science 2024 (L-R) – Fermín Serrano Sanz (ES), Snežana Smederevac (RS), Sofie Burgos-Thorsen (DK), Luciana Marques (BR), Mairéad Hurley (IE) Credit: Florian Voggeneder

Fermín Serrano Sanz (ES) coordinated the White Paper on Citizen Science for Europe and managed the Spanish portal ciencia-ciudadana.es. At the Ibercivis

Foundation, he has led or supported tens of projects integrating science, policy, society, art, and technology. A participant of the Future Innovators Summit, he was also Commissioner for the Agenda 2030 in Aragon, and now chairs the Working Group on Policy, Strategy, Governance, and Partnerships at the European Citizen Science Association.

Snežana Smederevac (RS) is Full Professor at the Department of Psychology, Faculty of Philosophy, University of Novi Sad, and Coordinator of the STAR Center of Excellence for Behavioral Research in Psychology. As former Vice-Rector for Science at the University of Novi Sad, she coordinated the first Open Science projects in Serbia, resulting in the National Open Science Policy. She is author of the first Open Science Manual and Guide for Citizen Science in Serbia. Her research focuses on personality psychology and behavioural genetics.

Sofie Burgos-Thorsen (DK) has a PhD in Sociology and has worked across urban strategy, participatory design, and digital innovation for the last 10 years. With projects like *Urban Belonging* (winners in 2023 of the Diversity award) and *South Park Youth Vision*, she tackles social and environmental justice issues and works with local communities to create equitable and resilient cities. She was a MIT scholar and R&D specialist in Gehl Architects before taking a role at the Techno-Anthropology Lab, researching Generative AI for citizen engagement.

Luciana Marques* (BR/ES) is Head of Communication at a biotechnology company. She is a journalist focused on science communication, with experience in the medical field and involvement in many European projects. Luciana's academic journey includes publishing in scientific journals and presenting at conferences.

Mairéad Hurley (IE) is Assistant Professor in Science Education in Trinity College Dublin. With her colleagues in Trinity's Science and Society Research Group, her work explores the role of science learning in shaping socially and environmentally just and sustainable futures, using participatory and transdisciplinary approaches. She integrates her own creative practice as a traditional musician to explore the potential for Irish traditional arts and folklore to inform contemporary environmental education and engagement.

*Luciana Marques was originally a member of the pre-jury, while Dr. Susanne Hecker was supposed to participate in the main jury. As Susanne fell ill at the last moment and was thus not able to travel to Linz, Luciana graciously agreed to step in and join the main jury at short notice. Due to this last minute change, Luciana was only able to join the jury meeting in person from Saturday, 27 April.

The 2024 pre-jury members

Enza Lissandrello is an Associate Professor in the Department of Sustainability and Planning at Aalborg University in Denmark. She has an academic background in urban planning, public policy, human geography, and the governance of socio-technical system innovation and transitions. She has been a senior lecturer in Italy, The Netherlands, Denmark, and France. Her main interest lies in planning to promote citizen participation and address issues of representation. Additionally, she serves as the research coordinator of the Urban Europe Research Alliance (UERA).

Dr. Susanne Hecker* is First Chair of the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) and head of the science programme Society & Nature at the Museum für Naturkunde – Leibniz Institute for Evolution and Biodiversity Science, Berlin, Germany. With a background in communication science, her research interests lie in citizen science and participation at the interface between science, society and politics and the role of communication in participative research projects.

Maria Leão is, since 2022, the coordinator of Ciência+Cidadã (C+C) Programme (<https://linktr.ee/cienciamaiscidadada>), implemented in a close partnership between NOVA ITQB, Gulbenkian Science Institute and Oeiras Municipality, with the mission of implementing a citizen science strategy in scientific institutions and local communities. She was for 10 years, between 2012 and 2022, one of the Executive Directors and Vice-President of Maratona da Saúde a non-profit association that aimed to raise awareness and funds for biomedical research in Portugal. She has a degree in Biology from Coimbra University, an International Master in Biotechnology by De Montfort University, a PhD in Virology and Cancer from Imperial College / Gulbenkian PhD Programme in Biology and Medicine (PGDBM) and a post-doc in breast cancer from the Breakthrough Breast Cancer Centre.

Ana Macedo, Medical doctor. PhD in Pharmacology. Invited Associate Professor. President of the Ethics Committee of the Algarve Biomedical Center. In 2023, she founded the WGSC, dedicated to Diversity, Equity and Inclusion. Author of several books and more than five dozen scientific articles; responsible for the research line, 'LGBTQIA+ Health and Medical Education Research Group', having won the 1st call of IMPETUS Accelerator in 2023, with the project 'Health Equity for LGBTQIA+ People'.

Sofia Morazzo International Clinical Research Center, St.Anne's University Hospital, Brno, Czech Republic. Faculty of Medicine, Masaryk University, Brno Czech Republic. Her involvement with citizen science has been mostly focused on motivating and inspiring young students at the high school level

or initial years of university, to understand how we investigate, in my case, metastatic cancer. Sofia believes that reaching out to young citizens could inspire them to pursue science but most of all equip them to better understand how research is done and enable them to be more critical about it. Sofia's involvement with citizen science is through the Echos Project (<https://cancermissionhubs.eu/>), a European Union project that aims to establish National Cancer Mission Hubs across Europe, to operate at local, regional and national levels, to bridge the gap between all the different stakeholders and facilitate the EU Cancer Mission.

5. Jury Statement

Elevating Communities and Excellent Research through Citizen Science – Paving the Way for Radical Societal Transformation

Mairéad Hurley (IE), Sofie Burgos-Thorsen (DK), Snežana Smederevac (RS), Fermín Serrano Sanz (ES), Luciana Marques (BR)

2024 is the second year that we honour the outstanding citizen scientists in Europe. Citizen Science, a collaborative approach involving volunteers from diverse backgrounds in scientific research, represents a trend and a key paradigm shift in contemporary science. At its core, Citizen Science embodies the democratisation of knowledge. Inviting participants from all walks of life to participate in scientific discovery transcends traditional boundaries of expertise, inspires curiosity, catalyses innovation across various disciplines, and empowers communities to actively contribute to our understanding of the world. This inclusive process fosters a sense of global citizenship, pride, ownership, empowerment, inclusion, and shared responsibility among participants. It enriches the scientific process with new perspectives, insights, and evidence-based decision-making while often driving social innovation, building capacity in local communities, and countering apathy and civic disengagement. Furthermore, Citizen Science is a powerful tool for scientific communication and education. It fosters a deeper appreciation of scientific methods and nurtures a society of informed, scientifically active citizens.

Citizen scientists contribute significantly to co-designing research methods, posing relevant questions, developing innovative tools, collecting data, collectively interpreting findings, and providing policy recommendations through hands-on research experiences and online platforms, performances, or workshops. As a result, the reality of Citizen Science in Europe today transcends the consolidated idea of projects being a mere database of collected georeferenced points on a map: Citizen Science builds strong bridges between policies and societies in Europe. This collaborative approach helps to close the gap between scientific expertise and public understanding, leading to more effective and inclusive policy-making processes. Nowadays, this is a crucial aspect, given the nature of contemporary challenges such as political polarisation, increased social marginalisation of minority groups, anti-European sentiments, or anti-science narratives that pose risks to our democracy, collaboration, and trust in science. In an era marked by the

proliferation of fake news, right-wing populism, and distrust in sciences, engaging different groups directly with science contributes to generating reliable data and results and to safeguarding democratic values. By empowering citizens to participate actively in the scientific process, these initiatives promote a culture of openness, accountability, and critical thinking—essential pillars of a healthy democracy. Through engagement in research activities related to issues that directly impact their communities, Citizen Science projects cultivate a sense of ownership and investment in the democratic process.

As jury members, the range of projects we reviewed allowed us a unique insight into the transformative potential of Citizen Science to shape the future of Europe. These awards are a testament not only to the achievements of individual citizen scientists, but also to the collective spirit of collaboration and discovery that drives this movement forward. We respect the dedication and passion of all participants in this competition, while highlighting those projects that have achieved excellence in Citizen Science. The winners showcased here come from more than 30 different countries. They exemplify ways that European citizens generate valuable knowledge across various scientific domains, addressing pressing societal issues. Congratulations to all. These initiatives demonstrate exceptional achievements, showcasing innovative methodological approaches and interdisciplinary collaboration.

We are living in profoundly turbulent times, and the events of recent years have shed light on the many processes and practices that need to be completely overhauled, given a tune-up, or put out to pasture. It is clear that doing things the way we have always done them will not suffice. Instead, we need to pay heed to the voices of those who are doing things differently, rebelling, imagining an alternative world, and, most importantly, taking action. The projects we have honoured are these trailblazers who act as beacons for others to follow—whether they are using emerging or immersive technologies in unexpected ways, embracing circular economy, taking control of healthcare, or fighting against the many forms of injustice and oppression by generating knowledge and furthering education.

It's crucial to underscore the ethics, transparency, and excellence in these initiatives—especially those that aim to safeguard citizens' basic human rights and to uphold research integrity in the digital age.

What next for Citizen Science

All of the projects we reviewed were inspiring. They also highlighted areas for further developments that would allow Citizen Science in Europe to be more impactful:

First, on the level of *citizen science methods*, we recommend more ambitious and inclusive approaches. Many Citizen Science initiatives could take inspiration from projects such as *SeaPaCS*, winner of the Diversity & Collaboration prize, and others, to allow and support citizens to engage in all project phases, from inception to completion. This is just one step that can improve collaboration and participation of citizens in science. Another step to overcoming extractive tendencies involves investing in a reciprocal, rather than one-way, relationship between citizens and scientists. This might entail designing capacity building, educational outcomes, or accountability metrics into the project scope, ensuring that scientists give back to the communities, whose participation and labour they heavily rely upon.

Second, on *the topical or thematic level*, we encourage more Citizen Science projects to address technological issues in society. While many projects use sensor technologies, Artificial Intelligence (AI), and digital media as tools or means to study other issues, very few projects investigate technological problems as their topic of concern. Yet, Honorary Mention recipients such as *Intelligent Instruments in Citizen Science* and *Eco-Bot.Net* exemplify that Citizen Science has much to offer regarding our understanding of the implications of AI, Generative AI, surveillance systems, social media platforms, and other digital technologies, and in relation to democracy, environmental policies, urban planning, social justice, and other burning issues. Here, Citizen Science could help us challenge and address the biases in digital technologies, and their power and role in society.

Third, Citizen Science could evolve further by integrating artistic practices, reconfiguring *how* knowledge is produced and going beyond conventional, linear scientific data collection and analysis modes. The project *Dreamachine* exemplifies this potential by using artistic installations and drawing exercises to invite citizens to report in new ways about their sensory experiences, allowing for novel scientific research within cognitive science. This demonstrates that art and Citizen Science can inform and inspire each other, creating a Citizen Science that transcends traditional boundaries. While many Citizen Science projects currently focus on documenting their rigor in methods and data, the field could benefit from an increased focus on exploring what the integration of artistic practices could do to reconfigure knowledge production through creativity and playful research.

In line with European values, Citizen Science projects must consider their impact on all members of society. Citizen Science should both serve and meaningfully engage with groups and communities that have very little contact with science, in order to avoid excluding them. By bridging these gaps, Citizen Science can become more inclusive and impactful, breaking down barriers and fostering social justice.

6. Grand Prize

The European Union Prize for Citizen Science Grand Prize recognises outstanding achievements in the advancement of knowledge through the empowerment of civil society and citizens in the development of the future. The Grand Prize is not limited to specific topics or themes. The Prize will be awarded to the most outstanding initiative according to the award criteria.

The European Union Prize for Citizen Science Grand Prize 2024 is awarded to **INCREASE: Intelligent Collections of Food-Legume Genetic Resources for European Agrofood Systems INCREASE Citizen Science Experiment (CSE)**

image2.Common_bean_six_different_colored_lines_on_bean@Elisa.Bellucci.INCREASE_consortium.jpg | Credits: @Elisa.Bellucci.INCREASE_consortium

Intelligent Collections of Food-Legume Genetic Resources for European Agrofood Systems INCREASE Citizen Science Experiment (CSE)

Kerstin Neumann (DE), Roberto Papa (IT)

The idea behind INCREASE is to make available Plant Genetic Resources (PGR), currently preserved only in gene banks, to a large number of citizens and stakeholders, developing a decentralised conservation system that involves citizens in a Citizen Science Experiment (CSE).

The INCREASE CSE focuses on two highly relevant topics, listed in SDG (Sustainable Development Goals) and Green Deal: agrobiodiversity conservation and food legumes cultivation/consumption, which is of pivotal importance for the transition towards a plant-based diet, a key element to contrast and mitigate the climate change crisis.

The INCREASE CSE explores thousands of different beans plant genetic resources PGR thanks to the help of citizens who contribute to data collection on an unprecedented number of different locations, helping to better understand, not only many phenotypic traits, but also the adaptation of common beans in different environments. The huge pool of images stored in the INCREASE CSE App is the basis for detailed image analysis using artificial intelligence and deep learning, involving citizens to develop image recognition, and enabling the identification and correction of potential errors during the decentralised conservation steps.

Citizens are invited to continue after their first participation by exchanging CSE varieties via the App with others, forming a decentralised PGR conservation community.

Image3.
INCREASE_clip1_screenshots3@INCREASE_consortium.png
Credits: @INCREASE_consortium

A high innovation of INCREASE CSE is based on the use of digital tools. For the first time, CS, done with PGR and crop growth, is assessed at home via an App (INCREASE CSA). Moreover, for the first time ever, the Standard Material Transfer Agreement SMTA can be accepted via an App. All texts, including INCREASE website's contents and the App, are accessible in different languages to reach participants from as many countries as possible. A dedicated team of the CSE email account is in constant contact with citizens in their native languages, which seeks constantly to improve the CSE experience through the feedback of participants, interacting directly with them, and providing support through social media. In these spaces, there is also an exchange of knowledge among the participants, especially mutual advice.

We consider communication and information crucial. Therefore, we believe in the importance of public restitution, communicating the outcomes of the research in which they contributed. Our commitment is based on communication through a simplified language. Participants must be aware of the importance of their contribution.

The pedagogical aspect in our project is not of secondary importance: we are strengthening the collaboration with schools and school garden associations in different countries through specific projects involving children and families.

By establishing a collaborative relationship, the experiment also contributes to bringing citizens closer to science, giving the opportunity to familiarise themselves with previously unfamiliar issues. For instance, the engagement of students tends to lead to the involvement of the whole family, introducing science in daily interactions. The experiential aspect of individuals demonstrates the potential of Citizen Science not only as a contribution to science, but also as a source of personal enrichment. We can say that our project contributes both to the production of knowledge and awareness.

The INCREASE project is also committed to raising awareness on issues related to nutrition and sustainability, and events with experts on the importance of legumes in our diet are held. This awareness is a stimulus to develop new healthy food habits and encourages self-production. For these reasons, INCREASE CSE can have a great social impact in several aspects.

Open Science & FAIR data sharing were adopted from the start. Altogether, our project showcases that it is possible to bring together European citizens, relevant associations, researchers, and policymakers along with NGOs under a common goal of improving agrobiodiversity, despite the resurgence of nationalism in Europe.

www.pulsesincrease.eu/experiment

<https://calls.ars.electronica.art/2024/prix/winners/12961/>

Project Credits

INCREASE Consortium – INCREASE project has received funding from the EU Horizon 2020 research and innovation program, under grant agreement no. 862862

Project Biographies

Dr. Kerstin Neumann (DE) is a biologist, leading the group “Automated Plant Phenotyping” at IPK since 2021. She has long-standing expertise in non-invasive high throughput phenotyping systems and their application to evaluate diverse cereal collections for abiotic stress tolerance (drought and heat), contributing to elucidate trait genetic architecture, trait relationships and trade-offs, to improve crops’ performances under stresses. She is also involved in the establishment and use of seed-proof gene bank of cereals and legumes genetic resources. This resulted in leading Work Package 6 in INCREASE and as such being coordinator of the INCREASE CSE, together with Prof Papa.

Prof. Roberto Papa (IT) is Full Professor of Agricultural Genetics, head of the AGROBIODIVERSITY Lab, at the Polytechnic University of Marche. His research focuses on the conservation and utilisation of agrobiodiversity and plant genetic resources. By applying genomics approaches and pioneering the use of “molecular phenotyping”, he contributed new knowledge on crop germplasm genetic diversity, on crop domestication and adaptation to different environments, and on evolutionary history of crop species (legumes and cereals). He coordinated several national and international projects on crop genetic resources, and he is currently leading the H2020 *INCREASE* project; he developed the concept of decentralized conservation of crop genetic resources and designed the INCREASE CSE, coordinating it together with Dr Kerstin Neumann.

Jury Statement

Statement by the jury of the European Union Prize for Citizen Science 2024: Mairéad Hurley (IE), Sofie Burgos-Thorsen (DK), Snežana Smederevac (RS), Fermín Serrano Sanz (ES), Luciana Marques (BR)

The Grand Prize winner this year is the INCREASE project. Its main goals include generating phenotypic data for over 1,000 bean plant genetic resources (PGR) lines in different European environments where citizen

scientists help decentralised conservation and enhance agrobiodiversity. This project demonstrates outstanding work on genetic diversity and adaptation within common bean cultivars by integrating DNA sequencing with the analysis of phenotypic data.

With its strong scientific foundation, this project exemplifies excellence in research that embraces Citizen Science. To achieve its goals, it will engage many citizens through a dedicated application for data collection and seed exchange—5,000 participants of different backgrounds, ages, and genders all across Europe are participating in the 2024 campaign.

The INCREASE project raises awareness of agrobiodiversity and nutrition. It educates participants and policymakers on sustainable agri-food production and consumption. Legumes play a crucial role in issues such as soil health and climate resilience in the face of food security and scarcity concerns.

The project has implemented a participatory research model with various levels of engagement tailored to accommodate participants' diverse levels of expertise. This approach enables feedback collection, support provision, and information dissemination to ensure sustainable citizen engagement. The inclusion of artificial intelligence for image analysis and the implementation of the Standard Material Transfer Agreement (SMTA) allows the compliance of international regulations for testing this innovative decentralised conservation approach. Its extensive cooperation across countries, the involvement of citizens from different regions, and engagement with regional platforms emphasize its European dimension and importance. Looking ahead, the jury expects this award to support the further development and innovation of the project, which subscribes to the ethos of empowering communities through decentralised seed storage, enabling them to regain control of their agricultural heritage. By democratising access to seeds and knowledge, INCREASE challenges the dominance of large agrochemical corporations and promotes agricultural resilience, sustainability, and food sovereignty.

Finally, the project's collaboration between citizens and major research centres is outstanding, and it exemplifies how top-tier centres are opening up their research processes for scientific excellence and social inclusion. In particular, members from local rural communities, including farmers who usually perceive themselves as outside the formal research process, contribute in a direct, meaningful and accessible way. Their traditional knowledge, passed down through generations, is a valuable agricultural research and development resource.

7. Diversity & Collaboration Award

The Diversity & Collaboration Award (€20.000) Awarded for excellence in grassroots approaches, explorative collaboration, cultural and gender diversity, community participation, stakeholder engagement and social inclusivity.

This category focuses on initiatives with transdisciplinary collaboration models that actively engage with or are initiated by a diverse range of stakeholders. Awarded initiatives will demonstrate a specific excellence in pushing the boundaries between civil society, citizens and science by engaging with local communities or taking a grassroots approach, and that display gender and cultural diversity, community participation, stakeholder engagement, and social inclusivity. Diversity & Collaboration award criteria:

- Diversity of partnerships and stakeholders
- Community engagement
- Quality and amount of citizen scientist involvement
- Transdisciplinary involvement
- Integration of citizen scientists into scientific process
- Sustainable collaboration
- Gender diversity & social inclusion

image4.1_Spring_Water@GiuseppeLupinacci.jpg | Credits: Giuseppe Lupinacci

SeaPaCS: Participatory Citizen Science against Marine Pollution

Chiara Certomà (IT)

SeaPaCS proposed a participatory citizen science project led by social and natural scientists that mobilises volunteers in data collection, elaboration and sharing on the biological consequences of marine plastic pollution (via in-situ samples collection for plastisphere DNA analysis, underwater video documentation of new ecological niches, plankton evaluation), and drafted a plan for sustainability-oriented practices based on interviews with fishermen and sailors in the coastal city of Anzio (Italy) on the Mediterranean Sea.

The innovative aspects of the project resided in overcoming the extractive approach in Citizen Science (citizens as “sensors”) by promoting a fully participatory process on the EU ACTION project model; advancing a multidisciplinary perspective and methods by combining cultural geography and oceanography; overcoming the problem of inaccessibility of the marine environment for lay citizens thanks to the collaboration with the LNI; tackling locally cogent issues already identified by stakeholders and mobilising their tacit knowledge; feeding the European database on genetic diversity on plastic debris, filling important knowledge gaps worldwide and especially for the Mediterranean Sea. SeaPaCS entailed a co-design phase with citizens, starting with artistic photos and videos exhibition; the data collection and result elaboration via citizens+scientists+sailors sailing boat expeditions for microplastic collection with a professional Neuston-net labs for genetic and chemical analysis; the collective expedition on a fishing boat for documenting

macro-plastic debris trawling, and in-depth interviews with fishermen; two working groups on collection and recycling system for marine plastic and protocol for CS that led to a number of follow-up international projects (notably the EU Call Culture Moves Europe “Tentacular Thinking. Experiencing underwater assemblages of culture and nature”; EU NEB “FishArt. Participatory Art for Anzio Fishermen’s Harbour”; the Horizon EU project “PartArt. Participatory Art for Ocean and Water”), scientific outputs publicly available and local initiatives.

<https://crowdusg.net/seapacs/>

<https://calls.ars.electronica.art/2024/prix/winners/10328/>

Project Credits

SeaPaCS has been funded by the European Union via the Horizon project IMPETUS4CS, coordinated by the DIGGEO@ESOMAS lab at the ESOMAS Department, University of Turin and with the support of the ESOMAS Public Engagement, partnered by the Italian Naval League Anzio and Raw-News, with the endorsement of the United Nation Decade of Ocean Sciences for Sustainable Development and the Municipality of Anzio. Special thanks to Saverio Lalli, Davide Rinaldi, Riccardo Aleandri, Giuseppe Certomà and Caterina Folco, Davide Rinaldi, Riccardo Aleandri, Giandomenica Becchio, Eugenio Monaco, Lorenzo Colantuono, Angelo Grillo, the fishermen of Anzio, the teachers and students of schools in Anzio (notably Valeria Schinzari, Anna Martinelli and Loretta Palomba), Martina Gaglioti, Luigi Ravioli, Massimo D’Eramo, Francesco Traversa, Andrea Petraghani Ciancarelli, Diego Capobianco, Ivan Martini, Francesca Massimi and Ivano Cotogno.

Project Biographies

SeaPaCS multisectoral team specialised in multidisciplinary and radically participatory exploration, documentation and engagement techniques and informal tools to identify contexts-specific matters of concern and, by building on tacit competencies of local actors and multisectoral design skills, attempt at turning these into transformative knowledge for just sustainability. Chiara Certomà is a social geographer at the Sapienza University of Rome with international expertise in participatory process, marine social science, and environmental governance; Federico Fornaro is former director at the LNI-Anzio, oceanic navigator and CEO of the international hard-news agency Raw-News; Luisa Galgani is a chemical oceanographer at the University of Siena with extensive global experience in ocean carbon recycling and plastic pollution; Alessio Corsi is an Egyptologist by training and research manager at the CNR ISMAR; Giuseppe Lupinacci is a free-lance photographer specialising

in underwater and marine photography, sailing instructor and oceanic traveller.

Chiara Certomà (IT) is assistant professor of socio-political geography at the University of Turin, with over fifteen years of research experience in participatory methods for science and policy making. Engaged in 9 active national and international research projects and coordinator of the European projects “SeaPaCS”, “FishArt” and “Tentacular Thinking”, as well as PI of the project Horizon EU “PartArt. Participatory Art for the Ocean”. Expert in citizen science, environmental governance, and social innovation for sustainability, and engaged in the field of marine social sciences, participatory processes and visual geography. She authored more than 30 papers and books.

Luisa Galgani (IT) is chemical oceanographer at the University of Siena with expertise in microbial biogeochemistry, ocean carbon recycling, and plastic pollution research. Former Marie-Curie Global fellow at GEOMAR Kiel. She is a member of the Education and Engagement Committee of the IUCN and the Association for the Sciences of Limnology and Oceanography (ASLO).

Federico Fornaro (IT) is former sports director of the LNI in Anzio, skipper, and sailing instructor. Over 20 years of experience in ocean navigation, 2013 Esprit Marin award for the Mini Transact solo crossing of the Atlantic. He is also CEO of the independent news agency Raw-News (Italy-UK based) with over 18 years of experience in documentaries and worldwide hard-news. He is a permanent Italian correspondent for Al Jazeera and NBC News; and recurring correspondent for CBS, Euronews, Sky, CCTV, France24, BBC.

Alessio Corsi (IT) is technical manager of research at the CNR ISMAR, a qualified Egyptologist with international experience in archaeological field work management and a great passion and competence on marine biology.

Giuseppe Lupinacci (IT) is a free-lance photographer specialising in underwater and marine photography, skipper and ocean sailor, with working experience in the Maldives, Turkey, Egypt, Antigua, Barbados, Martinique, Sint Maarten, Saint Lucia, Tenerife. Authors of three photographic exhibitions in SeaPaCS. His photographic catalogue “Making Science Public. Participatory Explorations on Plastic Entanglements with Life in the Mediterranean Sea”.

Jury Statement

Statement by the jury of the European Union Prize for Citizen Science 2024: Mairéad Hurley (IE), Sofie Burgos-Thorsen (DK), Snežana Smederevac (RS), Fermín Serrano Sanz (ES), Luciana Marques (BR)

SeaPaCS explores the consequences of marine plastic pollution on local biodiversity via a participatory Citizen Science process in the coastal city of Anzio, Italy. It engages more than 250 fishermen, North African migrants, school children, teachers, environmental NGOs, marine lawyers, sailors, and divers in co-producing knowledge about the health of the Mediterranean Sea, contributing to scientific fields like oceanography, cultural geography, and marine chemistry. In doing so, the project demonstrates excellence in engaging a diverse range of stakeholders and innovating transdisciplinary collaboration models between them, pushing the boundaries between civil society, citizens, and science.

SeaPaCS is especially exemplary for centering a community-led grassroots approach and for its attention to overcoming extractive tendencies in Citizen Science (citizens as “sensors”), by involving citizens beyond plastic sampling and data collection in activities such as plastisphere DNA analysis, documenting underwater ecological niches, creating photo and video exhibitions, testing DIY microplastic trawling instruments, and building marine plastic recycling stations. SeaPaCS hereby demonstrates how we can involve citizens not just in mapping problems but also in taking collective action towards restoring biodiversity and ecological resilience in European oceans, with attention to social inclusion and cultural diversity. For these reasons, we honour SeaPaCS with the Diversity & Collaboration Award.

8. Digital Communities Award

Image 5. The Restart Project. Credit: The Restart Project / Mark Phillips

CoAct for Mental Health

OpenSystems group (ES)

CoAct for Mental Health is a citizen science project in which people experiencing mental health problems and their families are placed at the centre. The project is aligned with World Health Organization demands for enhancing community-based approaches in mental health services. The participation of people with lived experience of mental health problems is key to transform mental health worldwide.

32 people with mental health problems and family members have become Co-Researchers and have co-designed the first citizen science chatbot. The CoActuem per la Salut Mental (CoAct for Mental Health) Telegram Chatbot has shared hundreds of micro stories written by the Co-Researchers. The micro stories are mental health first-hand experiences on social interactions with close family, friends, workmates, neighbours, etc.

Image 2Xatbot@CoAct_consortium.jpeg | Credits: CoAct_consortium

The aim of the chatbot is to engage a wider public and learn about the chatbot participants' feedback. The chatbot has facilitated the continuous collection of responses from hundreds of participants over several years, in a private and safe space. The participants contributed to data collection that explores social support networks in mental health. These networks are grounded on social interactions, and they facilitate recovery processes, improve the quality of life, and act against social exclusion.

Face-to-face sessions with Co-Researchers were designed to interpret the data from the chatbot. During a final assembly with a wide mental health community, 14 recommendations were delivered to high-level local and regional representatives, and they were also published in the form of European and local policy briefs. The project is framed within a citizen social science defined as participatory scientific research co-designed and driven by groups sharing a social concern. The transdisciplinary research proposed combines social sciences methods such as auto-ethnography with a computational social science approach, including complex systems and networks theory.

<https://coactproject.eu/>

<https://calls.ars.electronica.art/2024/prix/winners/12948/>

Credits

We want to thank the 32 Co-Researchers, the 900 chatbot participants and the 50 organisations and institutions involved; the discussions and work with Santi Seguí, Hayat Said, Constanza Jacques; and Canòdrom (Barcelona council) for hosting the project.

CoAct for Mental Health is part of CoAct funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation program under grant agreement No. 873048. From 2023, the project has received partial financial support through grants PID2019-106811GB and PID2022-140757NB-I00 funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by "ERDF A way of making Europe".

Biographies

CoAct for Mental Health (ES) was led by the research group OpenSystems from the Universitat of Barcelona (Josep Perelló, Isabelle Bonhoure, Franziska Peter, and Anna Cigarini). OpenSystems develops citizen social science projects and involves communities in vulnerable situations. Salut Mental Catalunya has been a key partner as a civil society organization that represents people with mental health problems and their relatives (Bàrbara Mitats). The 32 Co-Researchers joined the project through an Open Call in 2020. They were involved in all research steps and in the results dissemination, as experts-in-the-field. The Knowledge Coalition, made of representatives of organisations involved in mental health care provision, were involved from 2020 to late 2022. Other key members: Itziar González-Virós (participation and cooperation), Pau Badia (chatbot drawings) and Verity Harrison (storytelling).

Josep Perelló (ES) is the project leader of CoAct. He is full professor at the University of Barcelona (UB), researcher at the UB Institute of Complex Systems (UBICS). He is also the founder and research leader of the OpenSystems which develops projects with citizen participation and artistic practices. He has been the responsible and the curator of the Laboratory Space in Arts Santa Mònica for the UB (2009-2012), the coordinator of the Barcelona Citizen Science Office of the Barcelona Council until 2019, and one of the curators of the Barcelona Science Biennale 2019 and 2023, among others.

Isabelle Bonhoure (ES) is the CoAct for Mental Health project coordinator. She is a researcher and coordinator of the OpenSystems group at the University of Barcelona (UB), which she joined in 2013, after a PhD in Materials Science and research and science communication experiences in multiple fields. She was involved in more than a dozen local, national, and European citizen science projects, focusing on citizen science co-creation processes in

schools and in public libraries, experimentation in public spaces, and citizen social science projects with citizens' groups in a vulnerable situation.

Jury Statement

Statement by the jury of the European Union Prize for Citizen Science 2024: Mairéad Hurley (IE), Sofie Burgos-Thorsen (DK), Snežana Smederevac (RS), Fermín Serrano Sanz (ES), Luciana Marques (BR)

CoAct for mental health stood out to us as an excellent example of citizen social science, involving patients with lived experience of mental health issues, and their families, as co-researchers and co-producers of evidence on their experiences of social support networks in their communities. The project developed an open-source chatbot as a tool for autoethnography, demonstrating great innovation and creativity in using digital technology to support and foster inclusive community building.

These citizen researchers contributed their daily micro-stories to create a body of evidence that aims to shift the paradigm for mental health care away from a biomedical approach towards personalised medicine and a community-centered approach, showing that social support networks can be deployed in mental health care for recovery, well-being, crisis management, and to prevent isolation and exclusion. A small and dedicated core group of 32 citizen scientists participated throughout the entire life cycle of this co-creation project, from inception to data analysis and interpretation, and even participating in presenting the resultant policy recommendations, while a further 900 citizens used the chatbot to engage with the research.

*This project allows citizens to play an active role in research that directly impacts their lives and harnesses the power of technology to include marginalised voices as active participants in the transformation of mental health care. Technology in this case facilitates the participation of citizens in developing a personalized approach to healthcare and medicine. Overall, the *CoAct* project fosters an open and inclusive civil society by empowering their community to critically engage with digital technologies—a worthy winner of the 2024 Digital Communities award.*

9. Honorary Mentions

The selection of Honorary Mentions is not shaped by thematic considerations but, consist of outstanding initiatives from all fields and directions of Citizen Science. Beyond the quality assessment of applications, the selection of Honorary Mentions will also consider the geographical diversity as well as the diversity of contexts and research fields represented by the selected initiatives. In 2024 the jury selected 27 Citizen Science Initiatives from all submissions to the European Union Prize for Citizen Science to be awarded Honorary Mentions.

ASD Publics: Playable cities for all

Raquel Colacios (ES), Blanca Calvo Boixet (ES)

<https://calls.ars.electronica.art/2024/prix/winners/10732/>

ASD Publics and PAtB are pioneering initiatives aimed at enhancing the design and accessibility of public spaces for neurodiverse children, particularly those with autism spectrum disorder (ASD). ASD Publics employs a holistic approach, incorporating nature-based solutions and innovative design strategies to create sensory-friendly environments. It employs a collaborative co-creation methodology involving autistic children, families, urban practitioners, policymakers, and autism experts. The project has developed design guidelines to promote inclusivity and sustainability, raising awareness and empowering the Autism Community in the process.

PAtB, building on ASD Publics, focuses on enhancing the accessibility of public play spaces, particularly toy libraries in Barcelona. Collaborating with the autism community, city officials, and designers, PAtB prototypes and tests autism-friendly play infrastructure, adapting both structures and toys. It aims to deepen understanding through real-world testing and open engagement events, providing open-access design manuals.

Both initiatives highlight the significance of citizen engagement, interdisciplinary collaboration, and data-driven decision-making in addressing neurodiversity and public space accessibility. By leveraging collective expertise, they envision vibrant, inclusive environments that celebrate diversity and promote well-being. ASD Publics and PAtB serve as models for community-driven urban planning, inspiring cities globally to embrace neurodiversity in their designs.

<https://asdpublics.eu/en/>

Credits

We extend our sincerest appreciation to all the families and children who participated in the research activities of the project. Our heartfelt thanks go to our collaborators Aprenem Autisme and Escola Industrial de Sabadell for their invaluable involvement. Lastly, we express gratitude to the New Europe Bauhaus and the European Institute of Technology for their generous support of the project.

Biographies

Raquel Colacios (ES) Raquel is an architect and urban designer, she holds a PhD by the Universitat Internacional de Catalunya in Barcelona. She is co-founder of the firm Taab6 in Barcelona. She is currently a researcher at TURBA research group at UOC Barcelona, and assistant professor at UMEA University in Sweden, visiting lecturer at KU Leuven and TU Darmstadt. Her research and line of action is based on architectural and urban design as a tool for social and environmental justice.

Blanca Calvo Boixet (ES) Blanca Calvo-Boixet is a researcher and PhD student at Universitat Oberta de Catalunya. She focuses on the inclusion of vulnerable people in city-making from the lenses of architecture and urban planning. She co-led the project ASD Publics, which aims to improve public space for children with autism and their families.

Jury Statement

Statement by the jury of the European Union Prize for Citizen Science 2024: Mairéad Hurley (IE), Sofie Burgos-Thorsen (DK), Snežana Smederevac (RS), Fermín Serrano Sanz (ES), Luciana Marques (BR)

The ASD Publics project in Barcelona embraces citizen science principles, actively involving autistic children and families in intervention design of parks and playgrounds. Collaborating with the Aprenem Association engages participants from IGAIN's patient pool and Play Aut the Box phase, fostering ongoing collaboration. Empowering autistic individuals as co-creators promotes inclusivity and understanding, echoing the ethos of citizen science in amplifying diverse voices.

Bellingcat: A Collective Of Citizen Journalists Using Open Source Data To Investigate Matters Of Public Interest

Bellingcat (NL)

<https://calls.ars.electronica.art/2024/prix/winners/12483/>

Bellingcat uses open-source research techniques to uncover facts that are in the public interest. They look to share the knowledge and skills we learn with the wider public so that they can do the same.

Together, Bellingcat and its community have investigated potential war crimes in Ukraine Ethiopia, Armenia and Yemen. We have detailed police violence in Colombia and the United States. They have revealed lax security measures at US military bases in Europe that host nuclear weapons. Furthermore, their work has uncovered how state-backed Russian assassins have been operating in Europe and that Russian secret service operatives sought to poison the opposition politician Alexei Navalny. In recent months Bellingcat have been investigating the perils of generative artificial intelligence (AI). Their work has exposed groups using AI tools to create non-consensual deep fake nude images of unsuspecting women. Bellingcat's reporting led to some of these websites being shut down. They have also detailed how Russian ships were exporting Ukrainian grain from sanctioned ports in Crimea before transferring their cargo at sea to avoid detection.

All of these investigations revealed information that was important to the wider public and increased knowledge of topics that were hitherto murky or unknown. Bellingcat continue to refine their methods as technology advances and share their techniques with the wider public. Bellingcat believe a growing community of open-source investigators focused on information integrity, identifying wrongdoing, debunking dis-and-misinformation as well as spreading the word on news literacy can only be a force for progress and good.

<https://www.bellingcat.com/>

Biographies

Bellingcat (NL) Bellingcat is a collective of open-source investigators that seeks to carry out open-source investigations and train others to do the same. The project was founded in 2014 and have carried out high profile

projects that have exposed war crimes, narco-traffickers and state-backed violence.

Jury Statement

Statement by the jury of the European Union Prize for Citizen Science 2024: Mairéad Hurley (IE), Sofie Burgos-Thorsen (DK), Snežana Smederevac (RS), Fermín Serrano Sanz (ES), Luciana Marques (BR)

Global community of over 23,000 citizen journalists from more than 20 countries combining the art of writing with the scientific accuracy of investigative journalism. Its latest investigations use open tools to cover many facts like war crimes in Ukraine or state violence all around the world.

BP100: Community and Architecture Festival

Hungarian Contemporary Architecture Centre (HU)

<https://calls.ars.electronica.art/2024/prix/winners/10031/>

Budapest100 is an annual festival launched in 2011, celebrating and preserving the city's architectural heritage with strong community involvement. It promotes the idea that every building is significant, drawing around 10,000 visitors yearly and encouraging community engagement and knowledge sharing. The festival goes beyond architectural appreciation by fostering social cohesion and dialogue about urban issues.

The event's organisation starts each year with research on buildings based on archival materials and selected themes, such as the centenary of 1910s buildings, the Grand Boulevard, river embankments, public spaces, Bauhaus heritage, Buda Castle, and, most recently, late modern heritage.

Volunteers, recruited through an online call, participate in a 4-month mentoring program to develop necessary skills. Their tasks include engaging with residents and organising activities like history walks, community picnics, exhibitions, and games. The festival culminates in a celebratory weekend in May, highlighting the city's tangible and intangible heritage, as well as its residents.

Budapest100 fosters sustainability and community-driven actions beyond the festival, as residents and volunteers continue organising community events and initiatives. The project stands out for its community focus, distinguishing it from other European heritage events. It inspires citizen involvement in

renovation and urban planning, promoting sustainable cities and communities, while catalysing dialogue about urban issues, and inspiring the establishment and strengthening of residential communities.

The festival showcases scientific quality, social impact, diversity, communication, innovation, and a European dimension. Recognised by the European Heritage Awards/Europa Nostra Awards in 2023, Budapest100 exemplifies inclusive, participatory initiatives addressing community, heritage, and urban challenges.

<https://budapest100.hu/>

<https://kek.org.hu/>

Credits

Budapest100's success is reflected in over 650 opened buildings, 2,200 volunteers, and around 160,000 visitors in 14 years. Its annual budget of €30,000-35,000 is mainly provided by the National Cultural Fund of Hungary and the Municipality of Budapest, with small additions by district councils and private sponsors. The event's organisation is led by a 15-member team consisting of 2 project leaders, 1-2 research leaders, 3-5 volunteer coordinators, a communication and PR specialist, a website content manager, and experts responsible for the urban walks and the professionals' day.

Biographies

Hungarian Contemporary Architecture Centre (HU) KÉK (Hungarian Contemporary Architecture Centre) is an independent institution focused on architecture, urban development, and their relation to communities. With 15 years of experience and a vast partnership network, KÉK plays a pivotal role in Central Europe's architectural culture. Their strength is the combination of wide-range participation, complex analysis, and innovative content development. KÉK organizes exhibitions, conferences, festivals, and community events, and manages long-term projects like community gardens. The experts of KÉK participate in advisory roles in urban development programs and architectural projects.

Jury Statement

Statement by the jury of the European Union Prize for Citizen Science 2024: Mairéad Hurley (IE), Sofie Burgos-Thorsen (DK), Snežana Smederevac (RS), Fermín Serrano Sanz (ES), Luciana Marques (BR)

BP100 is an annual festival in Budapest which celebrates the city's heritage by asking citizens to open up their historic buildings and sharing personal

experiences of the architectural history. With 13 years and 160,000 visitors, this project shows the power of citizen science to gather typically hidden knowledge from citizen historians in an accessible way.

Carnivore Tracking Project: Involving volunteers in wolf and lynx monitoring

Rosan Miroslav Kutal (CZ), Michal Feller (CZ), Romana Uhrinová (SK), Barbora Černá (CZ), Carnivore Conservation Programme, Friends of the Earth Czech Republic (CZ)

<https://calls.ars.electronica.art/2024/prix/winners/13453>

The Carnivore Tracking Project focuses on involving volunteers in data collection on three large carnivore species - wolves, lynx and bears. The recovery of these large carnivores in Europe's human-dominated landscape is a challenge for successful coexistence and the ability of human society to tolerate charismatic keystone species in forest ecosystems, but also species that are the source of many local conflicts, especially in areas with high livestock densities.

Many conflicts at the local level stem from prejudices, legends, disinformation and fear of the unknown about large carnivores, especially in areas that have been recolonised by large carnivores in recent years and where local people have no personal experience of sharing the landscape with them.

Typical characteristics of large carnivores are their low population densities, large home ranges and nocturnality, which make encountering them and estimating their abundance, population density or feeding ecology extremely difficult and expensive in terms of human resources. This is where volunteer citizen scientists, if properly trained, motivated and organised, can provide valuable assistance.

Friends of the Earth Czech Republic's Carnivore Conservation Programme started as a volunteer initiative to (1) protect lynx and wolves from poaching, (2) collect reliable data on their occurrence by snow tracking and collecting other indirect signs of their presence such as scat or hair, and (3) involve local people in data collection and non-formal education about large carnivores.

Each year, training for new volunteers is organised as 3-day workshops in several areas recently recolonised by large carnivores and field data collection is organised through smaller monitoring events or individually throughout the year.

The scientific quality of the project is high: the data have generated new knowledge published in high-impact journals such as Science, PloS ONE, Scientific Reports or Conservation Letters.

<https://www.selmy.cz/>

<http://www.carnivores.cz/>

Credits

We are grateful to all the dedicated volunteers of the Carnivore Tracking Project and the following institutional and financial support.

Institutional: Mendel University in Brno, Charles University, Czech University of Life Sciences, Institute of Vertebrate Biology, Nature Conservation Agency (CZ), NP Šumava, NP Krkonoše, NP České Švýcarsko.

Financial: Ministry of Environment (CZ), European Union, Interreg Central Europe, Ministry of Education Youth and Sport (CZ), EuroNatur Foundation, Ministry of Interior (CZ), Liberecký region, Olomoucký region, Karlovarský region, Moravskoslezský region, Active Citizens Fund.

Biographies

Carnivore Conservation Programme, Friends of the Earth Czech Republic (CZ): The Large Carnivore Conservation Programme is a local group of Friends of the Earth Czech Republic (Hnutí DUHA). The NGO was founded in 1992 by students of Palacký University in Olomouc, formerly known as the Olomouc local group. It has been actively involved in the protection of large carnivores for the past 20 years, as wolves have returned to the Czech Carpathians (Beskydy) and have now recolonised many other parts of the Czech landscape.

Miroslav Kutal (CZ) started working as a volunteer citizen scientist in 2002 while studying biology and ecology at Palacký University in Olomouc. He started coordinating wolf and lynx patrols, a forerunner of the Carnivore Tracking Project and developed the initiative in the following decades. Miroslav completed his PhD on wolf and lynx ecology at the Mendel University in Brno and currently works as an academic researcher focusing on large carnivore ecology and conservation, using citizen science data for research. He is involved in the Carnivore Tracking Project as a scientific advisor.

Michal Feller (CZ) graduated in biomedical and ecological engineering at Brno University of Technology. Since 2018, he has been employed by FoE CZ as a monitoring coordinator in the Jeseníky Mountains. He also held the position of Programme Manager and now he is the coordinator of FoE CZ, where he is responsible for the coordination of the organisation together with the Programme Manager. Michal is also responsible for the implementation

of project activities, and he continuously participates in the training events relevant to the Carnivore Tracking Project in the area of Jeseníky.

Romana Uhrinová (SK) studied ecology at Comenius University in Bratislava. During her studies, she also volunteered to monitor large carnivores in NP Muránska Planina in Slovakia. From 2020 to 2023, she worked for WWF Slovakia as a project manager for large carnivores. Since April 2023, she has been working as a Programme Manager at FoE CZ, where she focuses on the conservation and monitoring of large carnivores. Her involvement in the Carnivore Tracking Project is mainly focused on the coordination of local coordinators, who are responsible for volunteer training.

Barbora Černá (CZ) has been monitoring wolves in FoE CZ since 2016, mainly in the area of Podbezdězí, Kokořínsko and Ralsko. During 2018-2020, she also worked for the Agency for Nature Conservation and Landscape Protection of the Czech Republic on a project relevant to the topic of the Wolf in Human-Altered Transboundary Landscapes and subsequently until 2023 as a researcher for the Institute of Forest Ecology at the Faculty of Forestry and Wood Technology of Mendel University in Brno. Barbora has been coordinating the Carnivore Tracking Project in FoE CZ since 2020.

Jury Statement

Statement by the jury of the European Union Prize for Citizen Science 2024: Mairéad Hurley (IE), Sofie Burgos-Thorsen (DK), Snežana Smederevac (RS), Fermín Serrano Sanz (ES), Luciana Marques (BR)

Monitoring programme for three large carnivore species –wolves, lynx and bears– in the Czech and Slovak Republics engaging local communities in multiple ways and providing significant scientific results since 2002. Also, its communication and engagement models mark this as a remarkable example of how to bring together different groups, such as local nature enthusiasts, artists, students or hunters.

CITIZENS FOR SDG 15.1

Ivana Radović (RS)

<https://calls.ars.electronica.art/2024/prix/winners/13195/>

According to the European Environment Agency (EEA), the EU has on average around 25% of land as protected areas. In Serbia this percentage is around 8% and process of protection of areas is very slow (it can last up to 10 years). The project tested the potential of citizen science to respond to the problem - how to overcome lack of resources and to provide data about biodiversity and habitats in a fast and economically acceptable way. Project contributes directly to the SDG 15, Target 15.1., indicator 15.1.2

Project had a significant scientific impact, on a global and national scale: research resulted in finding of 6 new animal species for the world and 12 new animal species for Serbia. Project provided high quality data - around 98 % of data points are verified by experts. The quality of data is recognised by different stakeholders, including decision makers, who decided (based on our report) that they will visit this protected area and analyse the possibilities for expansion of the protected area. This policy impact can result in significant environmental impact - proposed area for protection is around 5 times bigger than the current protected areas. During the project was formed community of citizen scientists. The project managed to gather the local community, including people from rural areas, older people and youth. The project was promoted and well accepted in the public. Results of this project can be upscaled on national, EU or even global level, as a good methodology approach for increasing the percent of protected areas. This kind of project is crucial for solving the crisis of biodiversity, which results in habitat and species loss, but also in solving the problem of disconnecting people from nature.

<https://impetus4cs.eu/citizens-for-sdg-15-1/>

Credits

This project was funded as a part of the first cohort of IMPETUS' acceleration programme. IMPETUS is funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 101058677. We also would like to express our gratitude to the Faculty of Biology, University of Belgrade (Serbia), for expert support provided to this citizen science initiative.

Biographies

Ivana Radović (RS) (master's degree in biology and PhD in Agriculture) is a researcher in the field of plant physiology and works at the Faculty of Agriculture, University of Belgrade. She is also a director of an NGO Ecological movement "Frame of life" which works in the field of sustainable agriculture, agrobiodiversity and wildlife biodiversity conservation. In 2019 Ivana founded the first Community Seed Bank in Serbia - initiative for in situ conservation of traditional varieties of fruits and vegetables. She published more than 50 scientific publications.

Jury Statement

Statement by the jury of the European Union Prize for Citizen Science 2024: Mairéad Hurley (IE), Sofie Burgos-Thorsen (DK), Snežana Smederevac (RS), Fermín Serrano Sanz (ES), Luciana Marques (BR)

This Serbian initiative, led by the NGO Ecological Movement "Frame of Life," focused on expanding the protected area of the Monument of Nature Ribnica through citizen science. Citizens for SDG 15.1 empowers diverse communities to monitor and protect biodiversity around protected areas. With 29 citizen scientists, including women and elders, supported by 13 experts, the project collected data through group fieldwork, resulting in the discovery of 12 new species in Serbia, 1 new genus in Serbia and 6 new species for science. Based on the discoveries of the citizen scientists, recommendations were submitted to the relevant legal entity to expand the protection of this unique ecosystem to an area about five times larger.

Cultural Reforesting: How can we (in the west) renew our relationship with nature?

Dr. Sarah Edwards (GB), Andrew Franzkowiak (GB), Dr Kim Salmon (GB), Arji Manuelpillai (GB), Adam Kammerling (GB), Jess Ihetojeh (GB), Dr Will Pearse (GB), Dr Tilly Collins (GB), Stephanie Hot (GB), Heather Ackroyd (GB), Dan Harvey (GB), Eloise Moody (GB), Vicky Long (GB), Abigail Hunt (GB), Finn Chatwyn-Ross (GB), Kinship Workshop (GB), Harun Morrison (GB), Kim Coleman (GB), Connor Butler (GB), Dawn Stevens (GB), Andrew Merritt (GB), Bryony Bengel-Abbott (GB), Nestor Pestana (VE)

<https://calls.ars.electronica.art/2024/prix/winners/11627/>

Cultural Reforesting, stewarded by the London Local Authority of Richmond, comprises of exhibitions, artist commissions, scientific research and integrated participation exploring the ecological crisis from biodiversity loss and climate to environmental justice and wellbeing. Responding to the provocation - how can we renew our relationship with nature?

Much of Cultural Reforesting has focused on Orleans House Gallery, a remarkable ecosystem of contemporary art, riverside woodland, and colonial building; a ground zero for applied research on the ecological crisis. Artists and scientists engage with diverse participants and a variety of experimental experiences from working with children in care to learning about indigenous knowledge immersed in a range of urban spaces and therefore ecosystems. An imperative is the requirement of our culture(s) in the west to evolve, returning to nature, collaborating with the more-than-human world, centring upon Ethnobotany led by Dr. Sarah Edwards, author of 'The Ethnobotanical: A world tour of Indigenous plant knowledge' (2023).

The wider programme has supported 15 projects since 2020, some of these include:

Andrew Merritt's, SupermarketForest, challenges the idea of the supermarket, and where food comes from through sculpture and interactive design. Participants, including local school pupils, gathered data about their own ecosystems, with the project imagining what might grow to transform the ecosystems into revered forests.

Bryony Ella's art/science practice works with drawing and storytelling as powerful tools to centre us as part of nature. Her project develops 'wild drawings' to emotionally connect with the more-than-human across our local woodland.

Nestor Pestana's, in collaboration with bat expert Stephanie Holt, explores how empathy with bats might offer us new ways to tackle the ecological crisis. Amongst others, Nestor collaborated with Liisa Holmberg, Sámi leader, comprehending First Nation storytelling as important knowledge transition.

Through participation they have empowered participants to co-create imaginative responses to global climate crisis. They brought policy makers into the programme with other public services such as Parks, Planning and Climate, these collaborations are making an impact Borough-wide. The project has prioritised working with vulnerable young people – those who are economically disadvantaged and those in care.

<https://www.orleanshousegallery.org/cultural-reforesting/what-is-cultural-reforesting/>

Credits

Richmond Arts Service and the London Borough of Richmond upon Thames would like to thank; the team at Richmond Arts Service, the teams across the Local Authority, particularly Parks, Planning, Climate and Community Engagement, Achieving for Children, the more-than-human world, Kew Gardens, Richmond upon Thames College, Orange Tree Theatre, Royal

College of Art, London College of Communication, Royal Holloway, St. Mary's University.

Funding from Natural Environment Research Council, London Borough of Richmond upon Thames, St. Mary's University and all the in-kind support from 1000's of others.

Biographies

Dr. Sarah Edwards (GB) is an ethnobotanist with an interdisciplinary background. Sarah is based at the University of Oxford, teaching ethnobiology and biological conservation. Much of Sarah's teaching is based on insights gleaned from working on collaborative ethnobiology projects with First Nations communities in northern Australia. Of Romani and Irish Traveller heritage, Sarah is also a Trustee of the charity London Gypsies and Travellers. Sarah is lead author of the book *Phytopharmacy: An Evidence-Based Guide to Herbal Medicinal Products* (2015) and *The Ethnobotanical* (2023).

Andy Franzkowiak (GB) is an award-winning creative producer and curator who specialises in science/art projects and site-specific works. He has delivered a range of programmes exploring our relationship with nature, with participation and collaboration across disciplines and with the more-than-human world foundational to his work. His work includes the critically acclaimed Enlightenment Café, a series of multidisciplinary art and science collaborations. He has presented work at Barbican, Tate Modern, Somerset House and in site specific locations, including Wakehurst, Kew Gardens.

Andrew Merritt (GB) work explores social and environmental issues via everyday scenarios criss-crossing the boundaries between the visual arts, architecture and activism. Through permanent installations, functional sculptures and public performances, projects provide a framework or foundation for communities and ecologies to build upon. Works mimic the everyday to act as familiar starting point and then take the subject into new realms. Merritt is one half of Something & Son. He has exhibited at Tate Britain; Tate Modern; Manchester International Festival; Gwangju Biennale, South Korea.

Bryony Ella (GB) is a British-Trinidadian artist, curator and producer working at intersection of art and science, focusing on nature connection. Her practice spans street art to oil paintings, textile design to drawing, playing with pattern, scale and composition, and moving between symbolism, abstraction and expressionism in the search for immersive encounters with nature. She also brings a strong community engagement and participatory focus to her public realm-based work. Bryony has 15 years' experience of curating and producing social history and science exhibitions, most recently leading the inaugural public engagement strategy for exhibitions at the UK's largest lab, The Francis Crick Institute.

Nestor Pestana (VE) is an educator, art director and digital designer, whilst developing a new media arts and research practice. My interest lies on the creative possibilities of new and emerging technologies - in how they can be used as storytelling tools to communicate ideas, concepts and create new interactions. Projects are research based, focusing on the necessity for critical engagement with contemporary and emerging issues, mainly related to technology and ecology. To facilitate this Nestor uses worldbuilding and design fiction frameworks, combined with storytelling methodologies.

Jury Statement

Statement by the jury of the European Union Prize for Citizen Science 2024: Mairéad Hurley (IE), Sofie Burgos-Thorsen (DK), Snežana Smederevac (RS), Fermín Serrano Sanz (ES), Luciana Marques (BR)

This UK-based initiative, Cultural Reforesting, offers a holistic approach to addressing the ecological crisis by engaging citizens in reconnecting with nature. Through collaborations with artists, scientists, and diverse communities, the project fosters awareness and understanding of our impact on ecosystems. By integrating participatory citizen-led programs, including exhibitions, artist commissions, and scientific research, Cultural Reforesting empowers citizens to take action in combating climate change. The initiative's emphasis on cross-generational engagement and partnerships including academia, arts organisations and local government agencies demonstrates its commitment to fostering social capital and influencing policy.

Domestic Heat Comfort for Energy Poverty and Climate Adaptation

Yağız Eren Abanus (TR), Sinan Erensü (TR), Duygu Dağ (TR), Cemre Kara (TR), Barış Türkddoğan (TR), Meryem Uyaver (TR), Elif Bengi Güneş (TR), Oğulcan Kınalı (TR), İlknur Akgül (TR), Daniela Kızıldağ (TR), Gülnaz Yücel-Durmuş (TR), Merve Özhan (TR), İdil Besler (TR), Tuğba Uçar (TR), Mekanda Adalet Derneği (Center for Spatial Justice) (TR)

<https://calls.ars.electronica.art/2024/prix/winners/13620>

Our project is a contribution to the climate & social justice struggle to increase people's resilience, influence public opinion through creative storytelling methods, and raise the awareness of policymakers by producing quantitative and qualitative data on the vulnerability regarding energy poverty and heat waves. In June 2023, we launched the project "Domestic Heat Comfort for Energy Poverty and Climate Adaptation" to explore the experiences of individuals and households about the heat in Istanbul, with the help of citizen

science methods. As part of this research, we provided heat and humidity sensors to a community of 32 households, with a specific focus on individuals from disadvantaged groups, such as the elderly, women, and children under 14. Using this equipment, we monitored the physical conditions these households were exposed to during the summer months. Furthermore, we also conducted interviews with participants to produce qualitative data about their experiences.

We compiled and examined this information and used it to produce datasets and a report. We also created a second community called “facilitator citizen scientists”, mostly consisting of higher education students and active citizens. We consulted this group to obtain additional support and perspectives to support our project's research design, its implementation, and the creation of interview questions. Our citizen scientists also participated in home visits and played a role in analysing the data collected.

To gain further insights from our participating communities, we organised two capacity-building activities to facilitate community building and engage with different stakeholders about the issues surrounding increasing summer temperatures.

To also help us spread our message and increase the visibility of the issue on social media, we organised a closing event, produced two podcasts, and a video detailing our key findings and the potential health issues of increasingly warmer summers.

<https://mekandaadalet.org/program/enerji-yoksullugu-ve-ev-ici-isi-konforu/>

Credits

Our project was initiated thanks to the support of IMPETUS.

IMPETUS is funded by the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 101058677.

Our project also was supported within our involvement in the Urban Doers Community which is an initiative of the DUT Partnership.

Biographies

Mekanda Adalet Derneği (MAD) (Center for Spatial Justice) (TR) founded in 2016, the MAD has quickly become a prominent non-profit dedicated to tackling the issues of urban and environmental justice through a rights-based approach. Emerging from the collective efforts of action researchers, the Centre initially focused on post-earthquake recovery and anti-eviction efforts. Since then, it has expanded its mission to include broader environmental justice initiatives. Our goal is to foster fair and sustainable urban and

ecological environments through transdisciplinary research, and advocacy bridging the gap between academia, activism, and the public.

Yağız Eren Abanus (TR) graduated from Kadir Has University Faculty of Law. During his undergraduate studies, he volunteered in organisations such as Kadir Has University Theatre Community, Good4Trust, and Green Thought Association. He continues his amateur and professional civil society and lawyering work in different organisations. He works as an expert in the Environmental Justice Program of the Centre for Spatial Justice with a special focus on climate justice. The main areas of his work are climate laws, just transition, heatwaves, energy poverty, energy democracy, community building, and green economy.

Sinan Erensü (TR) received his PhD in Sociology from the University of Minnesota. His dissertation looked at the changing relations of nature, society, state and capital in Turkey through analysing infrastructure investments and ecological struggles in the Eastern Black Sea Region. He co-edited the book *Reasons of Water: Neoliberal Politics and Struggles of Water-Energy in Turkey*. His research interests include development and ethnography of energy, environmental sociology and sociology of space, and urban and rural political ecology. He is a member of the Centre for Spatial Justice.

Duygu Dağ (TR) completed her undergraduate education in the Department of Visual Arts and Visual Communication Design at Sabancı University. For many years, she worked in the architecture and media sectors. She is a volunteer at Team Conscience (Vicdan Takımı), a group that aims at children's and young people's empowerment through sports. She works at the Centre for Spatial Justice.

Cemre Kara (TR) graduated from Mimar Sinan Fine Arts University Urban Planning Program. She joined MAD as an intern in 2018 and continued to work at the Environmental Justice Program since then. She aims to integrate her hopes relating to spatial justice into her life.

CONTRIBUTORS OF THE PROJECT

Barış Türkdoğan (TR) is a fourth-year student at Boğaziçi University, where they pursue a double major in Economics and Sociology. During their undergraduate studies, Barış has worked as a research assistant at the university's Sociology Data Lab and has volunteered in various organisations as Boğaziçi University Social Services Club (BUSOS), Boğaziçi TV, and Vote and Beyond (Oy ve Otesi). Their main research interests include political economy/sociology, urban sociology, and the sociology of culture.

Meryem Uyaver (TR) is a senior student at Bogazici University, pursuing a double major degree in sociology and history. She is a member of the Sociology Data Lab in her school, where she has been working on family forms and fertility in Turkey from a quantitative perspective. Nonetheless, her interests also expand to heritage studies and urban sociology, with a focus on

gender and identity. Meryem took part in various volunteering organisations, including Bogazici University Social Services Club, where she had the opportunity to conduct ateliers with children from diverse backgrounds.

Elif Bengi Güneş (TR) after graduating from Middle East Technical University's Department of City and Regional Planning in 2020, she earned her Master's degree there in 2023 with a thesis on the climate vulnerabilities of Syrian migrants in Istanbul. Since 2020, she has worked as a research assistant at Gebze Technical University, focusing on low-carbon urbanisation, fair climate and energy policies, urban political ecology, and sustainable urban transformation to promote inclusive and fair solutions for all and sustainable solutions for nature.

Oğulcan Kınalı (TR) graduated from the civil engineering department in 2012. He worked in zoning and urban planning directorates in various municipalities. He is currently working in the zoning and urbanisation directorate of Bakırkoy Municipality. He is also a member of the Chamber of Civil Engineers and has served on various commissions there. He is passionate about conducting research and studies in urban sociology and urban justice.

Tuğba Uçar (TR) was born in 1996 in Istanbul. She graduated from the department of Sociology at Middle East Technical University. Tuğba has volunteered for Tarlabaşı Community Centre which engages in right based activities. Currently, she is a volunteer at the Centre for Spatial Justice. Since 2021, Tuğba has been working at Postane, an urban centre for impact-driven work and joint cultural production based in Galata, Istanbul.

İlknur Akgül (TR) graduated from Ankara University's Sinology Department, she began her journalism career at Sabah Magazine Group. She has written books and held roles such as media coordinator in the publishing industry. Since 2017, she has been working freelance as a copywriter and content producer. She has enhanced her skills through workshops in scriptwriting, poetry, text analysis, and social media management. Previously, she was Co-Spokesperson for the Green Left Party in Şişli. She volunteers for initiatives like the Climate Justice Coalition, and Disaster Solidarity Volunteers.

Daniela Kızıldağ (TR) is a Master's student of sociology at Boğaziçi University, where she holds her bachelor's in philosophy and sociology. Her research interests include environmental sociology, climate change, and human-animal relations. She is a member of the Polen Ecology Collective.

Gülnaz Yücel-Durmuş (TR) in 2020, she graduated from Istanbul University, Department of Political Science and International Relations and completed his Master's degree in International Relations at the National Defence University with a thesis titled "Environmental Security and Climate Change Related Migrations: Afghanistan". In 2023, she started her master's at Boğaziçi University Institute of Environmental Sciences. She has worked as a researcher and project coordinator in non-governmental organizations. She is

academically interested in the Taliban-US peace process, climate change, and environmental security.

Merve Özhan (TR) is an educator, architect, and urban designer focused on mobility. At Arkki Türkiye and Bilgi University, she mentors students in architectural excellence and computational design. As the founder of InkluTech Design Studio, she leads sustainable product initiatives, combining diverse design techniques. Her research at C-MUS covers air travel management and urban dynamics, with a thesis on Istanbul's New Airport. She also bridges academia and municipalities, promoting participatory research and urban engagement.

İdil Besler (TR) is a Marketing Analytics Executive with a background in consultancy and e-commerce field in one of the biggest q-commerce companies in the world. Strong analytical mindset and communication skills with expertise in leveraging data insights to drive strategic marketing decisions and enhance business growth. She is also passionate about raising awareness using data visualization, she volunteered to visualise femicides in Turkey for the UN Women's #OrangeTheWorld campaign.

Jury Statement

Statement by the jury of the European Union Prize for Citizen Science 2024: Mairéad Hurley (IE), Sofie Burgos-Thorsen (DK), Snežana Smederevac (RS), Fermín Serrano Sanz (ES), Luciana Marques (BR)

This project focuses on addressing energy poverty and extreme heat vulnerability through a participatory research framework. By engaging citizens from diverse backgrounds in Istanbul, the initiative aims to quantify disparities in domestic heat comfort and resilience to extreme heat events in Istanbul. Through the deployment of heat and humidity sensors in households and qualitative interviews, the project generates valuable data to influence public opinion and inform policymakers. The project's most significant impact lies in its innovative approach to tackling climate and social justice issues. By addressing these questions, the initiative contributes to climate justice advocacy and informs policy discussions on climate adaptation and urban resilience.

Dreamachine: A major interdisciplinary programme fusing world class artists with leading scientific researchers.

Collective Act (GB), University of Sussex (GB), University of Glasgow (GB)

<https://calls.ars.electronica.art/2024/prix/winners/14008/>

Dreamachine is a major interdisciplinary programme fusing world class artists with leading academic researchers. In a unique collaboration, their team of architects, composers, technologists, scientists and philosophers set out to explore and chart our inner worlds, with the aim of sparking insight, reflection and curiosity. Created by Collective Act, the programme includes a groundbreaking scientific study investigating perceptual diversity, and a 5* reviewed immersive experience designed to take audiences on a magical journey into their own minds.

Inspired by an extraordinary but little-known flickering light device invented in 1959 by Beat-artist Brion Gysin, Dreamachine is the first immersive experience in the world designed to be viewed with your eyes closed. With spatial design by Turner-prize winning artists Assemble and a score composed in 360° sound by Grammy-nominated composer Jon Hopkins, the experience generates a luminous inner world of colours, patterns and dreamlike imagery using just white light. As you close your eyes, a bath of light and sound weave seamlessly together to generate a richly technicolour internal world - created by the power of your own brain and completely unique to you.

Dreamachine is also generating an unprecedented body of research, exploring questions that have baffled, and divided, philosophers and scientists for centuries. Led by a team of scientists and philosophers at the Universities of Sussex and Glasgow, their large-scale citizen science programme, The Perception Census, is the first major scientific study of its kind to investigate how we each experience the world in our own unique way - including how we perceive time, our beliefs about consciousness, and our sense of self. To date, 100,000 sections have been completed by 35,000 people, totalling over 50,000 hours of public participation in new scientific research – with participants from over 100 countries, aged 18, to 80. These findings will now support major new studies on the nature of perceptual experience, unlocking powerful new insights into the human mind.

<https://dreamachine.world/>

Credits

Dreamachine was originally commissioned by UNBOXED: Creativity in the UK with funding from UK Government. The Perception Census data analysis and review is supported by the Leverhulme Trust.

Dreamachine Lead Collaborators:

- Jennifer Crook, Director
- Assemble, Spatial Designers
- Jon Hopkins, Composer
- Dev Joshi, Technical Director

- Chris Shutt, Sound Designer
- Holition, Creative Technology Studio
- Professor Anil Seth, Scientist
- Dr David Schwartzman, Scientist
- Professor Fiona Macpherson, Philosopher
- A New Direction, Education Partner

Perception Census Credits:

- Production, direction, development and marketing: Collective Act. Core team: Lydia Entwistle, Tara Simmonds, Willow Williams, Erin Wolson, Dev Joshi, Jennifer Crook.
- Website Design: Project Simply
- Scientific Development: University of Sussex and University of Glasgow. Core team: James Alvarez, Reny Baykova, Trevor Hewitt, Fiona Macpherson, David Schwartzman, Anil Seth
- Animation: Guy Chase, Shay Hamias, Meital Miselevich

Biographies

Collective Act (UK) Dreamachine was created by award-winning producers of powerful large-scale participatory commissions. The project create emotionally engaged, meaningful shared experiences that bring people together and transform the way we look at the world. Dreamachine champion a collaborative and multi-disciplinary approach to producing new work, creating space for taking risks and the unexpected to bring ambitious ideas to life. Collective Act is led by Jennifer Crook, an internationally renowned Producer and Director who has led critically acclaimed public projects for festivals and arts organisations around the world, creating multi award-winning interdisciplinary commissions with artists including Olafur Eliasson, Danny Boyle, Christo and Jeanne-Claude and Jeremy Deller.

The scientific and philosophical research underpinning the Dreamachine programme and The Perception Census is led by world-leading academics Professor of Neuroscience Anil Seth from the University of Sussex and Professor of Philosophy Fiona Macpherson from the University of Glasgow. It is overseen by Professor Anil Seth’s team at the Centre for Consciousness Science, University of Sussex, and is supported by more than 20 collaborating researchers around the world.

Funded by the European Union

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Professor Anil Seth (UK) is a neuroscientist, author, and public speaker who has pioneered research into the brain basis of consciousness for more than twenty years. He is a Professor of Neuroscience at the University of Sussex, Co-Director of the Canadian Institute for Advanced Research Program on Brain, Mind and Consciousness, a European Research Council Advanced Investigator, and Editor-in-Chief of the academic journal *Neuroscience of Consciousness*. He has published more than 200 research papers and is recognised by Web of Science as being in the top 1% of researchers in his field in the world.

Dr David Schwartzman (UK) is a Senior Post-Doctoral Research Fellow at the University of Sussex Centre for Consciousness Science. He is a cognitive neuroscientist, whose research investigates the neural basis of altered states of consciousness. His PhD specialised in the analysis of electrical signals from the brain using EEG and investigated the functional role of high frequency brain activity (gamma oscillations) in visual perception.

Professor Fiona Macpherson (UK) FRSE, MAE, is Professor of Philosophy at the University of Glasgow, and Director of the Centre for the Study of Perceptual Experience (CSPE). She is president of the British Philosophical Association, a trustee of the Kennedy Memorial Trust, and a member of Arts and Humanities Research Council and the UK Research and Innovation Creative Industries Advisory Group. Her research concerns the philosophical nature of consciousness, perception, illusion, hallucination, imagination, and technological interventions on the senses including VR and AR.

Jury Statement

Statement by the jury of the European Union Prize for Citizen Science 2024: Mairéad Hurley (IE), Sofie Burgos-Thorsen (DK), Snežana Smederevac (RS), Fermín Serrano Sanz (ES), Luciana Marques (BR)

Immersive experience and large-scale global study that allowed thousands of visitors and participants to engage with academic researchers in a pleasant way. This programme allows to co-create an artwork while helping researchers to address new scientific questions around topics like consciousness or perception.

Eco-Bot.Net - Defending The Digital Environment

Barnaby Francis (GB), Robert '3D' Del Naja (GB), Dale Vince (GB)

<https://calls.ars.electronica.art/2024/prix/winners/13495/>

Eco-Bot.Net is a collaborative initiative aimed at systematically analysing greenwashing and climate disinformation on social media platforms like

Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter. Developed with input from data scientists, technologists, journalists, artists, and litigators, the platform aggregates, exposes, flags, and visualises extensive data. This data, publicly accessible, equips researchers, press, litigators, and policymakers with robust evidence to hold fossil fuel companies and social media platforms to account. The project identified a significant knowledge gap in advocacy, press, and litigation sectors regarding systemic greenwashing analysis, particularly highlighted during COP26. Adhering to the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity and EU GDPR frameworks, it emphasises ethical and legal data handling. Recognized for its innovation, Eco-Bot.Net won 'Innovation of the Year' at the 2023 British Journalism Awards.

The project employs novel data scraping and ML/AI analysis to address a critical knowledge gap in advocacy, journalism, and litigation sectors. Integrating arts and creative processes provides a unique cultural perspective on pioneering data science work. Eco-Bot.Net is the world's first public platform offering comprehensive analysis and transparency of greenwashing and climate disinformation at scale.

Eco-Bot.Net utilises advanced AI and ML tools to monitor and analyse social media data from high-emission actors and sectors globally. During COP26, the project provided intelligence briefings to the UK COP26 presidency team. It offers real-time data analysis and visualisation to support investigative journalism and climate litigation, revealing hidden targeting data in greenwashing campaigns. By creating a public evidentiary archive, the project aims to influence discourse and policy, making information accessible to a broad audience.

The project fosters cross-sectoral collaboration among diverse professionals, including artists, journalists, litigators, academics, technologists, designers, and policy experts. The team includes nine nationalities with 34% female representation. During COP26, participants tagged and verified over 3,000 data records. Inclusive decision-making ensures active collaboration among diverse partners. In December 2023, Eco-Bot.Net secured funding to develop the project into a Climate Ad Archive with Oxford University's Human Centred Computing department and Climate Litigation Lab, enhancing evidentiary data collection and validation at scale.

Eco-Bot.Net has established media partnerships with major outlets like The Guardian, Time Magazine, New York Times, and New Scientist, achieving over one million views from news articles. The project promotes knowledge sharing through workshops and trainings, and participatory workshops during beta testing helped refine the platform. Innovative data visualisations

ensure accessibility and comprehension for a wide audience, with public campaigns launched during COP26 further amplifying its reach.

Eco-Bot.Net supports the European Green Deal's goal of climate neutrality by 2050 and reducing emissions by 55% by 2030, aligning with the 2023 European Commission plans to require evidence-backed green claims for products. The platform also supports the UN's call to end greenwashing, providing data sets and analyses to EU member states, the UN, journalists, and litigators on greenwashing communications by major polluters.

In 2023, new partnerships with Oxford University expanded data collection and developed the project's evidentiary databases for global class action litigation, with the Climate Ad Archive set to launch in Autumn 2024.

<https://eco-bot.net/>

Credits

PARTNERS:

Institute For Strategic Dialogue - <https://www.isdglobal.org/>

Jennie King - Lead Researcher
Lukasz Janulewicz - Analyst
James Peel - Legal Advisor

Francesca Arcostanzo - Data Scientist

Centre For Analysis of Social Media (CASM) - <https://www.casmtechnology.com/>

Jeremy Reffin - Lead Data Scientist
Justin Crow - Data Scientist
Carl Miller - Research Director

StudioNeural - <https://studioneural.ai/>

Barnaby Francis - Project Manager

Ad.watch - <https://ad.watch/index.html>

Nayanatara Ranganathan - Lead Developer

Manuel Beltran - Lead Developer

RNDR - <https://rndr.studio/>
Jeroen Barendse - Consultant

Edwin Jakobs - Lead BE Developer

Climate Litigation Lab (CLL), Oxford University
- <https://www.smithschool.ox.ac.uk/oxford-sustainable-law-programme/research/climate-litigation-lab>

Benjamin Franta - Director

human centered computing, Oxford University - <https://hcc.cs.ox.ac.uk/>

Dr. Reuben Binns - Technical Supervisor

Hrishikesh Barman - Lead Data Scientist
Sruthi Viswanathan - RA
Neil Natarajan - RA

Tom Davier - RA

FUNDERS:

1 - COP26 Pilot (2020 - 2021)

Dale Vince
Arts Council England
European Climate Fund
Global Strategic Communications Council (GSCC)

2 - Eco-Bot.Net - Phase 2 (2023 - Ongoing)

European Climate Fund

KR Foundation

Biographies

Barnaby Francis (UK), known as Bill Posters, is a UK artist, author, and disinformation researcher. His work explores disinformation, persuasion architectures, and power dynamics in public spaces and online, using a network-based approach. Collaborating across arts, sciences, and advocacy, he engages in various projects including conceptual, intervention, and synthetic art. His Spectre installation with Dr. Daniel Howe won the Sheffield Doc/Fest 2019 Alternate Realities Award. Posters' viral synthetic media artworks sparked global press and unexpected official responses from Facebook, Instagram and Youtube. Posters founded StudioNeural, a new media and arts production company that specialises in applying emerging technologies and AI to the arts, advocacy, journalism and TV sectors.

Robert '3D' Del Naja (UK) is an artist, musician and activist most noted for co-founding Massive Attack; pioneering street art techniques; and multi-

disciplinary innovations in the use of data visualisation and AI technology, executed within the realms of art, music and documentary.

In 2020 Massive Attack commissioned The Tyndall Centre For Climate Change Research to create a roadmap to decarbonisation for the music industry.

Dale Vince (UK) OBE is the founder of Ecotricity and a United Nations Climate Champion. Born in Great Yarmouth, Norfolk, in 1961, he left school at 15 with no qualifications and spent the next decade living on the road in a variety of unusual vehicles. Dale has always been very active in Ecotricity but it hasn't stopped him getting involved in other environment-related projects. His unwavering passion for the planet and commitment to making positive change in key areas of food, transport and energy have seen him pioneer the following projects: Forest Green Rovers, The Nemesis, Electric Highway and his first book, Manifesto – part-memoir, part blueprint for the future of the planet. Dale explains how focusing on energy, transport and food can solve the climate crisis and change the way we live for the better in other ways, too.

Jury Statement

Statement by the jury of the European Union Prize for Citizen Science 2024: Mairéad Hurley (IE), Sofie Burgos-Thorsen (DK), Snežana Smederevac (RS), Fermín Serrano Sanz (ES), Luciana Marques (BR)

This multi-stakeholder initiative involving researchers, artists and journalists aims to identify and classify online content as corporate greenwashing or climate change disinformation. An innovative conjunction of collective empowerment and technology usage, this project addresses intersecting challenges – mis and disinformation and the role of media in our society, and the relationships between capitalism, geopolitics and anthropocentric climate change.

GALLANT: Empowering Glasgow Communities for Climate Resilience and Biodiversity Conservation

Ria Dunkley (GB), Florence Halstead (GB), Sarah Gambell (GB), Becky Duncan (GB)

<https://calls.ars.electronica.art/2024/prix/winners/13240/>

GALLANT (Glasgow as a Living Lab Accelerating Novel Transformation) is an ambitious five-year project funded through NERC's 'Changing the Environment' programme, led by the University of Glasgow. With a vision of

Glasgow as a living laboratory, GALLANT aims to design, implement, and test a scalable, translatable systems approach that addresses multiple environmental and well-being challenges in urban settings. The project, comprising five novel environmental Work Packages (WPs) alongside three cross cutting Workstreams (WSs), is designed to drive systemic transformation in post-industrial urban landscapes. Underpinning GALLANT's ethos was integrating nature into urban environments to deliver climate resilience, carbon mitigation, social, health, and well-being benefits while fostering innovation and economic development through a social and ecological lens.

As the Community Collaboration Research team for GALLANT, their role centres on facilitating a highly praised five-year community science research programme developed in collaboration with stakeholders across Glasgow. GALLANT's approach prioritises inclusivity, ensuring diverse community voices shape and participate actively in the research process. They engage with community groups, public sector organisations, local councils, and community organisations, fostering partnerships to drive social innovation and community building. Throughout the project, GALLANT conducted research activities divided into five phases, focusing on engaging communities as active participants and, where welcomed, as co-researchers. By valuing and incorporating diverse perspectives, local knowledge, and community input, their research methodology, which is a blend of creative and scientific practices, prioritises inclusivity and community-driven decision-making, resulting in impactful and relevant research outcomes. In January 2024, GALLANT initiated mini gatherings in 3 established hub areas to collaborate with participants to identify key themes and questions to shape our research projects. They commenced five projects to address local environmental challenges and foster community empowerment. GALLANT upholds the principles of open science, ensure the accessibility and interoperability of data, and contribute to Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), fostering environmental sustainability and societal well-being. GALLANT used innovative approaches to engage communities, blending creative and scientific practices to communicate research findings effectively. GALLANT values community input and believe that community involvement is crucial to the success of this project.

<https://communitycollabglasgow.co.uk/>

Credits

We give special thanks to the community collaborators, without whom this project would have been impossible.

We would also like to thank the community groups, organisations, and venues that supported us in our local research and the delivery of participatory workshops and the GALLANT Community Collaboration Steering Group for their guidance.

Thanks to the wider GALLANT team, notably Principal Investigator Professor Jaime Toney for supporting our research approach.

Thank you to the Natural Environment Research Council (NERC) for funding the GALLANT programme.

Biographies

Dr Ria Dunkley (GB) is a Senior Lecturer at the University of Glasgow's School of Education, specialising in Geography, Environment, and Sustainability. Her research is all about finding ways to help people engage with their environment and climate crises, and she's particularly interested in how communities can make a difference by taking sustainable actions. Dr Dunkley lead the Community Collaboration Research in GALLANT.

Dr Florence Halstead (GB) With experience spanning numerous research projects working directly with children, youth, families, communities and schools, Florence works across a broad spectrum of topics, most prominently Children's Rights, Social Justice, Sustainability and Climate Change. Primarily working at the interface between these, she takes a reflexive approach to her research and is able to respond to changing and challenging situations both efficiently and effectively. Dr Halstead is a Postdoctoral researcher within the Community Collaboration Research workstream in GALLANT.

Dr Sarah Gambell (GB) is a post-doctoral researcher with the GALLANT project and has a previous background in antiquities trafficking and management of cultural heritage assets in conflict. After completing her PhD investigating the long-term digital sustainability of digitised cultural heritage, she shifted her focus to data visualisations related to spatial mapping techniques. Dr Gambell is a Postdoctoral researcher within the Community Collaboration Research workstream in GALLANT.

Becky Duncan (GB) is a participatory facilitator & photographer, specialising in social documentary photography. Becky founded Open Aye CIC in 2010 to provide photography and participatory projects for Scotland's third sector. Becky led the photo voice walks that were part of the first phase of the GALLANT Community Collaboration Research.

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GALLANT project empowers Glasgow communities through citizen science, fostering collaboration and addressing social, environmental and economic challenges. GALLANT drives positive change through engagement activities, qualitative research and policy advocacy. The project work, including inclusive finance policy change and community wellbeing initiatives, has a tangible impact, promoting equity and sustainability.

HistorEsch: Citizen History Activities in the city of Esch-sur-Alzette

Thomas Cauvin (FR), Joella van Donkersgoed (NL)

<https://calls.ars.electronica.art/2024/prix/winners/11600/>

HistorEsch is a collaborative and participator project about the history of Esch-sur-Alzette (Luxembourg). HistorEsch aimed to co-create and share knowledge about the past using transdisciplinary, open and citizen science methods to actively engage the public during each phase of the project and promote sustainable collaboration between academia, citizens, institutions, and other stakeholders.

The innovative character of HistorEsch is demonstrated in the production of a mural, an audio tour, an exhibition, and a digital community (the FI'ESCH Back Facebook group). The interdisciplinary fresco project combined artistic practices with citizen science to co-create a mural at a social housing complex. The audio tour innovated the north-American project HearHere by exploring the possibilities to reach a multilingual society with local oral histories. The co-creation process for the exhibition allowed us to test the maximal extend of sharing authority. All project's outputs are publicly freely accessible aiming to create a lower threshold to engage with - and learn about history.

Further scientific impact was achieved through the organization of a European interdisciplinary workshop that was held on March 2023, together with a diverse group of public history practitioners we drafted a charter on participatory public history practices in the streetscape (historesch.lu/charter).

A central part of the social impact of our collaborative projects was the qualitative engagement with the citizens and the new bridges of trust built between academia, cultural institutions, and local residents. Not only did the public learn about (hidden) histories of their city, but they have also become empowered to contribute to historical research.

<https://historesch.lu/historesch/>

Credits

The HistorEsch project is part of Public History as the new Citizen Science of the Past (PHACS), a project funded by the Fond National de la Recherche ATTRACT fellowship for Thomas Cauvin. The HistorEsch activities we created in close collaboration with Nuit de la Culture, Kulturfabrik, and Ariel Beaujot and Michel Hamilton who are the drivers behind HearHere. The project's success is owed to the community members in Esch-sur-Alzette and our wonderful student-assistants.

Biographies

Thomas Cauvin (FR) is Associate Professor of Public History at Centre for Contemporary and Digital History (C²DH) at the University of Luxembourg. Head of the 'Public History and Outreach' Research Area at the C²DH, he is the ATTRACT fellow (funded by the Fond National de la Recherche, 2020-2025) for the [Public History as the new Citizen Science of the Past \(PHACS\)](#) project. Cauvin has been the president of the International Federation for Public History (2018-2021) and is the author of *Public History: a Textbook of Practice* (2016/2022).

Joëlla van Donkersgoed (NL) leads the [FNR PSP-Flagship](#) project called [Historesch Gesinn](#), which aims to build a social hub where the public can engage with historical research conducted at the Luxembourg Centre for Contemporary and Digital History (C²DH) and cultural institutions in Luxembourg. Prior to this project, she was part of Cauvin's PHACS-project. She holds a PhD. degree in Cultural Heritage and Preservation Studies from the Art History department at Rutgers, the State University in New Jersey, USA (2020), as well as a Bachelors and Master's degree with a specialisation in public archaeology and archaeological heritage management from Leiden University, the Netherlands (2012/2014).

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The HistorEsch project in Esch-sur-Alzette, Luxembourg, democratises city history by engaging citizens in co-creating narratives via murals, audio tours, and exhibitions. It involves the community throughout, bridging historical gaps and deepening heritage connections. With over 2,000 active citizens (5.9% of the population), its alignment with European Capital of Culture status signals broader policy impact. It fosters diversity and collaboration,

involving citizens, institutions, associations, and researchers. The Citizen Historian Circle ensures varied perspectives, while European partnerships and workshops highlight its broader scope.

iesaisties.lv: Citizen Science Platform for Humanities and Arts in Latvia

Krišs Salmanis (LV), Sanita Reinsone (LV), Eva Eglāja-Kristsons (LV), Ginta Pērle-Sīle (LV), Rita Grīnvalde (LV), Ieva Weaver (LV), Uldis Ķīrsis (LV), ILFA'S DH GROUP (LV)

<https://calls.ars.electronica.art/2024/prix/winners/9993/>

iesaisties.lv, curated and developed by the Institute of Literature, Folklore and Art of the University of Latvia (ILFA), is a digital platform for citizen science in the humanities and arts. It provides pathways for users to engage with different initiatives according to their interests and preferences, filtering by topics and types of participation.

iesaisties.lv aims to foster closer collaboration between humanities scholars and the public, thereby enhancing multi-directional knowledge exchange, collective creativity and engagement-based humanities. Secondary objectives include making humanities data openly accessible, developing digital skills, promoting a culture of participation and encouraging lifelong learning.

The citizen science initiatives represented by iesaisties.lv are carried out by ILFA in collaboration with different partners, including research organisations, governmental and municipal institutions, media outlets and NGOs. Among the partners are the Latvian National Commission for UNESCO, Institute of Mathematics and Computer Sciences of the University of Latvia, Latvian Open Technologies Association, and others.

For over a decade, through iesaisties.lv numerous citizen science initiatives have been implemented at the crossroads where citizen science meets cultural heritage and digital humanities, among them: (1) Knowledge-sharing initiatives where the general public or specific communities are invited to share insights on specific topics, helping to contextualise and uncover hidden historical narratives. (2) Creative-response initiatives encourage the public to engage with cultural heritage materials in creative ways that deepen their understanding of and interest in these subjects. (3) Crowdsourcing initiatives that encourage the public to put joint efforts in creating datasets necessary

for societal good or unlocking cultural history materials by participating in hands-on activities.

<https://iesaieties.lv/>

Credits

Project supported by Latvian Council of Science, project “Towards Development of Open and FAIR Digital Humanities Ecosystem in Latvia” (No. VPP-IZM-DH-2022/1-0002), implemented within the framework of the National Research Programme “Digital Resources of the Humanities”

European Regional Development Fund, project “Empowering knowledge society: interdisciplinary perspectives on public involvement in the production of digital cultural heritage “ No. 1.1.1.1/16/A/040

Institute of Literature, Folklore and Art of the University of Latvia: Sanita Reinsone (LV), Eva Eglāja-Kristsons (LV), Ginta Pērle-Sīle (LV), Rita Grīnvalde (LV), Ieva Weaver (LV), Uldis Ķīrsis (LV), Krišs Salmanis (LV), Sandis Laime (LV), Dace Bula (LV), Elīna Gailīte (LV), Madara Eversone (LV), Justīne Jaudzema (LV), Aigars Lielbārdis (LV), Ilze Ļaksa-Timinska (LV), Signe Raudīve (LV), Digne Ūdre (LV), Elvīra Žvarte (LV), Nils Graustiņš (LV), Ainars Brūvelis (LV).

Collaboration with Latvian National Commission for UNESCO (LV), Institute of Mathematics and Computer Sciences of the University of Latvia (LV), Latvian Open Technologies Association (LV), Punctum Magazine (LV), Latvia’s Centenary Office (LV).

Biographies

Sanita Reinsone (LV), head of Iesaieties.lv project and ILFA’s Digital Humanities group; humanities researcher with a deep interest in digital humanities, digital cultural heritage, citizen science and participatory research methods; studies also folk narratives, life-writing traditions, and oral history.

Eva Eglāja-Kristsons (LV), Iesaieties.lv coordinator of initiatives in literature (Read Aloud and Literatura.lv) and women’s history (Womage.lv). Her scholarly pursuits primarily encompass literary studies, distant reading, and autobiographical and biographical studies, focusing on the phenomena of celebrity and the dynamics of women’s activism and agency.

Ginta Pērle-Sīle (LV), Iesaieties.lv project manager; humanities researcher interested in digital humanities focusing on ways for transfer of scientific knowledge and raising awareness of cultural heritage in society; studies folk songs and the history of Latvian folkloristics.

Rita Grīnvalde (LV), a senior researcher and Head of the Archives of Latvian Folklore, ILFA. Her research interests include the history of folklore studies; heritage studies; folk religion; visual ethnography; cultural policy. Grīnvalde is involved in curation of lesaisties.lv knowledge exchange initiatives.

Ieva Weaver (LV), ethnomusicologist, a researcher at the Archives of Latvian Folklore, ILFA. Her main research interests are Latvian traditional music and its revival and contemporary uses, and the history and culture of Latvian Roma. Weaver is the main coordinator of the citizen science initiative documenting revival and exploration of the archival sound recordings in “Dziedi ar arhīvu” [“Sing with the Archives”] campaign.

Uldis Ķirsis (LV), a skilled developer who has been working with the development of ILFA's digital resources, including lesaisties.lv citizen science platform since 2014.

Krišs Salmanis (LV), a prominent Latvian contemporary artist, educated at the Art Academy of Latvia and the Academy of Media Arts in Cologne, has received several prestigious awards throughout his career. In addition to his artistic endeavours, Salmanis has contributed his design expertise to citizen science digital initiatives in collaboration with the Institute of Literature, Folklore, and Art of the University of Latvia

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"lesaisties.lv" is a decade-long citizen science initiative led by the Institute of Literature, Folklore, and Art (ILFA) at the University of Latvia. This digital platform fosters public engagement in humanities and arts projects, facilitating collaboration between scholars and citizens while preserving cultural heritage. It offers diverse activities such as transcribing historical manuscripts and creative-response campaigns, promoting interdisciplinary collaboration and societal inclusion across age groups and backgrounds. It showcases potential policy impact and community empowerment in cultural preservation through partnerships with NGOs, media, and governmental bodies like UNESCO.

Intelligent Instruments in Citizen Science: Understanding Contemporary AI through Creative Practice

Thor Magnusson (IS), Jack Armitage (GB), Halla Steinunn Stefansdottir (IS), Victor Shepardson (US), Nicola Privato (IT), Miguel Angel Rozzoli (AR), Halldor Ulfarsson (IS), Sean O'Brien (US), Marco Donnarumma (IT), Sophie Skach (AT), Giacomo Lepri (IT), Intelligent Instruments Lab (IS)

<https://calls.ars.electronica.art/2024/prix/winners/13116/>

Artificial Intelligence is becoming increasingly human-like and it is now proficient in a key human activity: musical creativity. But what does this mean? How does creative AI change our notions of art, culture and society? As new machine learning technologies begin to mirror ourselves, we need to look into that mirror and ask how this is changing us. The Intelligent Instruments project takes a pioneering step in AI research by answering how new creative AI transforms our relationships with technology and other people.

This ambitious vision is achieved by using music as a platform to establish public understanding of AI. Through three respective work packages, Intelligent Instruments are developing instruments with creative AI, exploring human-AI collaboration in music and they frame sonic instruments as scientific instruments. Grounded equally in technology development and the humanities, Intelligent Instruments engages with diverse disciplines by developing a theoretical framework of creative AI, initiating a discourse around human-centred creative AI, and defining principles of human-AI relations in services and products.

The aim of the Intelligent Instruments project is therefore to work in the public eye, to keep our lab open, and to disseminate work as it happens. They seek public engagement and investment in the research programme, as their research is relevant to the questions people are asking already, and to place the lab as a social hub where these questions could be explored in a safe, welcoming and open intellectual environment. Through the broad reach of music in society, they reach the general public and conduct citizen science with people in a field that people understand and engage with from a personal, emotional and intellectual manner. This is how Intelligent Instruments can ask these questions, explore the new ideas that are emerging, analyse the language and discourse, and be part of shaping how we understand creative AI in this unique historical moment.

<https://iil.is/>

Credits

The Intelligent Instruments project is supported by the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (Grant agreement No. 101001848). The project is hosted at the University of Iceland. Some workshops and public engagements have been funded by the Icelandic Music Fund.

Biographies

Thor Magnusson (IS) is a Professor in Future Music at the University of Sussex and a research professor at the University of Iceland. His work focusses on the impact of digital technologies on musical creativity, explored equally through practice, theory and education. Magnusson's research is underpinned by the philosophy of technology and cognitive science, exploring issues of embodiment, artificial intelligence, and compositional constraints in digital musical systems as practiced by musicians in concrete situations.

Jack Armitage (UK) is a musician, designer and technologist based in Reykjavík, and the founder of Afverhju Ekki - The Absolutely Everything Studio. Jack is a postdoc researcher at the Intelligent Instruments Lab, University of Iceland, and has a PhD in Media & Arts Technologies from Queen Mary University of London. Jack's work spans experimental concerts, electronic club performances and DJ sets, multimedia installations, interface design, sound design, music production and composition. Jack's project Lil Data is released on the PC Music label.

Halla Steinunn Stefansdottir (IS) is a postdoctoral fellow at the Intelligent Instruments Lab and active as a performer, composer and curator within contemporary music and ecological sound art. She recently obtained a PhD in artistic research in music from Lund University. Her research looked at agencies at play in artistic processes, explored through micro-labs set within and outside of institutional environments. She continues along such a context-sensitive trajectory at the lab, focusing on the mediation that occurs in the performance of an AI-augmented violin.

Victor Shepardson (US) is a doctoral researcher in the Intelligent Instruments Lab at LHI. Previously he worked as a machine learning engineer on neural models of speech, and before that studied Digital Musics at Dartmouth College and Computer Science at the University of Virginia. His interests include machine learning, artificial intelligence, electronic and audiovisual music, and improvisation. In his current research, he approaches the lived experience of people with AI via design and performance of new musical instruments.

Nicola Privato (IT) is a PhD candidate in Cultural Studies, conducting research at the Intelligent Instruments Lab. Previously, he studied Electronic Music at the Conservatory of Padua (MA), Jazz Improvisation and Composition at the Conservatory of Trieste (BA) and Modern Languages and Cultures at the University of Padua (BA). In the past decade he has been curating musical events and festivals, composing, performing and teaching music. His current

interests include alternative forms of notation, improvisation, composition, and Human-Computer Interaction in performative contexts.

Miguel Angel Crozzoli (AR) is a composer, saxophonist, and Ph.D. candidate in Cultural Studies, currently conducting research project at the Intelligent Instruments Lab in Reykjavik. He has studied European composition, jazz studies, and cultural management in Argentina, and holds an Advanced Postgraduate Diploma and a Master's degree from the Rhythmic Music Conservatory in Copenhagen, where he conducted practice-based research on sonification. His research in music, new technologies, data, and AI, explores the questions about the role of the arts in critical thinking and perception.

Halldor Ulfarsson (IS) is the luthier and technician of the Intelligent Instruments Lab. He is the inventor of the halldorophone, an electro acoustic string instrument intended for working with string-based feedback. For the past decade he has been seeking out and working with musicians to make music with halldorophones and noting their thoughts and feelings on the process to inform further development. He is currently funded by an innovation grant from the Icelandic Technology Development Fund on further development of halldorophones.

Sophie Skach (AT) is a postdoctoral researcher Intelligent Instruments Lab and the Queen Mary University of London, where she also obtained her PhD as part of the Media & Arts Technology programme. Trained as a fashion designer (BA, MA), she has worked in industry for larger companies as well as on her own projects. With this background in fashion and textile design, her research explores 'smart' clothing as a ubiquitous, wearable sensing system for applications in social interaction, soft robotics, and intelligent instruments.

Sean Patrick O'Brien (US) has a BFA from the Studio of Interrelated Media from MassArt in Boston and recently received a Master's in Performing Arts from Listaháskóli Íslands where he worked on interactive and kinetic sculpture in a performative and socially engaged practice. Inspired by the local Icelandic arts and music scene he has worked with the Reykavík Dance Festival, Sequences Art Festival, Nylistasafnið, Kling og Bang, Listahátið, Raflost, Rask, Mengi, Spectral Assault Records, and grassroots organizations Post-Dreifing, RUSL Fest, Fúsk, and King og Bong.

Giacomo Lepri (IT) builds digital instruments, plays with them and tries to critically think through them. His research crosses the domains of electroacoustic improvisation / composition, human-computer interaction and cultural studies. He holds a PhD in Media and Art Technology from Queen Mary University of London. At the Intelligent Instruments Lab he explores compositional strategies for the mediation of sociocultural values and technological agencies, considering the practice of sonic interaction design as an opportunity to play with illusions and magic.

Adam Pultz Melbye (DK) is a performer, composer, and sonic researcher. He creates solo double bass music, often with the FAAB (feedback-actuated

augmented bass)—a feedback double bass with embedded signal processing. He investigates how terms such as musical mastery, virtuosity, resistance, and failure may become reframed (or rendered obsolete) through the decentring of human agency. His work has been performed in the US, Japan, Australia and Europe and he appears on around 50 releases, three of these solo albums.

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The Intelligent Instruments project in Iceland (2021-2026) uses music to explore the impact of AI on creativity and society. The project addresses important questions about the implications of AI in relation to ethics, technology development and access to technology. It involves interdisciplinary collaboration, integrating insights from technology development and humanities. It engages citizens via open lab sessions, workshops, and performances, excelling in all aspects. Embracing interdisciplinary collaboration and open science practices, it fosters dialogue and shapes policy discussions. Feedback mechanisms ensure community input, while innovative approaches enrich the European research landscape.

kafsimo@karditsa, Activating citizens through biomass recycling into heating pellets

incommon (GR), Energy Community of Karditsa (GR)

<https://calls.ars.electronica.art/2024/prix/winners/11413/>

The kafsimo@karditsa project (kafsimo is a pun on the Greek words kafes=coffee and kafsimo=fuel) addresses environmental challenges by transforming coffee waste into renewable heat, thereby empowering the local community. Through the tangible utilisation of used coffee, the community observes how the cycle of an organic waste is closing - shifting the general perception from waste to valuable resources.

More specifically, the project activates citizens through the collection of coffee waste from cafés and combines them with municipal prunings in order to produce heating pellets. Part of these pellets feed a biomass boiler installed in a municipal building that houses a kindergarten, covering its thermal needs,

and part is offered free of charge to customers of the social grocery. As a result, the school community becomes the carrier of this participatory and innovative practice, sharing it with households and the rest of the local community.

The project's main objectives are to (1) raise awareness in a participatory way and change our mentality around organic waste, (2) produce a solid biofuel in line with the principles of the circular bioeconomy (3) close the coffee lifecycle by giving it back to its community, which with their involvement, trust is strengthened in new and innovative projects. The objectives are achieved through the synergy of a range of stakeholders and an ecosystem of local actors that are equally involved for the materialisation of the project, including: incommon, ESEK, CERTH (Centre for Research & Technology, Hellas), local cafés, the Municipality of Karditsa, and the wider local community who have embraced and supported the initiative since its initial steps.

This project indicates how social engineering, energy production and behaviour change can be combined and provide an easy, direct, understandable, and environmentally friendly solution.

<https://www.incommon.gr/project/kafsimo/>

Biographies

Incommon (GR) is a civil non-profit organization which supports local communities (citizens, schools, businesses and institutional actors) to speed up the transition from the current dominant linear to a circular model of life.

Energy Community of Karditsa (ESEK) (GR) is a citizen energy cooperative, established in 2010. It counts more than 400 members and since 2018 has been producing biofuels in the form of pellets and distributing them to the local society while engaging all the local stakeholders in order to create a value chain, an ecosystem of local actors.

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The project aims to create a circular economy model by converting coffee waste into renewable heat, promoting sustainability, and fostering community engagement. It involves collecting coffee waste from local cafes, combining it with municipal prunings, and producing heating pellets. These pellets cover the thermal needs of a kindergarten and are distributed free to

customers of a social grocery. Engaging various stakeholders, including local cafes and the Municipality of Karditsa, the project emphasises inclusivity and active participation. By diverting coffee waste from landfills and reducing CO2 emissions, it aligns with European policies on the circular economy and sustainability.

Language Checkers - This is how we speak in Neckarstadt: Die Sprach-Checker – So sprechen wir in der Neckarstadt

Janin Roessel (DE), Christine Möhrs (DE), Elena Schoppa-Briele (DE), Rahaf Farag (EG), Heike Chan Hin (DE), Theresa Schnedermann (DE), Sprach-Checker team at the IDS (DE)

<https://calls.ars.electronica.art/2024/prix/winners/10845>

As modern societies are increasingly diverse due to mobility and migration, so are linguistic landscapes—but understandings of multilingualism and lived realities are limited; deficit-oriented views predominate. Multicultural communities harbour linguistic treasures that are often overseen, and little attention is paid to the voices of the people living there—particularly those of young residents.

In this project “Die Sprach-Checker”, children and adolescents from Neckarstadt-West, a very diverse district in Mannheim, become citizen scientists. Our goal is to raise awareness for their linguistic treasures and to transform deficit-oriented views into mutual appreciation of multilingualism. The young citizen scientists (re)discover their own languages and the language use in their environment—together with linguists and professionals. Language Checkers guiding principle has been to consider participants as co-scientists while co-generating research questions and jointly conducting research. Activities span from a book project to the training and implementation of scientific methods (e.g. storytelling, linguistic landscaping, language biographical interviews), and involve diverse collaborations (e.g. local stakeholders, schools, rappers).

Another aim is to make insights and outputs accessible to the community (e.g. at a summer festival of languages or an annual literary festival). Outputs, such as a children’s book or explanatory videos, are available online to inspire scientists and practitioners alike.

The project has emerged as a door opener for change: Their citizen scientists expressed surprise for and acknowledgement of their own language

treasures. Social media activities carried project's insights and appreciation for multilingualism to broader audiences. These are stepping stones for transforming deficit-oriented (self-)views and making citizen science more visible and approachable. The project is set to empower youth, build trust (in science), and contribute to the SDGs.

<https://www.ids-mannheim.de/zfo/dz-deutsche-sprache/sprachforschung-und-citizen-science/>

Credits

We would like to thank all citizen scientists. We are further grateful for the support we received after being awarded as one of the three best citizen science projects in the German competition "On your marks! Citizen Science in your city" (2022/23). Thanks to a donation from Neckarstadt Kids and the GBG Sponsorship Prize we were able to continue our project. We would like to express our deep gratitude to all our collaborators. Neckarstadt Kids, Campus Neckarstadt-West, Alte Feuerwache, and Marie-Curie-Realschule provide continued support in terms of personnel, space, and input.

Biographies

Christine Möhrs (DE) studied German linguistics, social psychology, and business administration at Leibniz University Hannover. In 2013 she earned her doctorate in German linguistics. She has been a research associate at the Leibniz Institute for the German Language since 2009, focusing on vocabulary, lexicography, corpus linguistics, and comprehensible language. Her work combines research with practical application. She heads the projects "Language Research and Citizen Science" and "The Language Checkers", both of which successfully and heart-warmingly promote participatory research.

Elena Schoppa-Briele (DE) studied theatre science, philosophy, and German literature at the Gutenberg University of Mainz and Ludwig Maximilian University of Munich. In her career, she has been involved in various language-related fields of activity: e.g. lecturing German, developing and coordinating training programmes for teachers and language courses. Since 2019, she has been a leading project manager for the "Forum Deutsche Sprache"(Eng. German Language Forum)—a planned science centre and a sustainable hub for diverse citizen science endeavours in Mannheim, such as "Die Sprach-Checker".

Janin Roessel (DE) studied psychology and business administration at the University of Mannheim, Germany, where she also pursued her doctorate. After her postdoc period in social psychology, she started at the Leibniz Institute for the German Language in 2022 and entered the project "Language

Research and Citizen Science” in 2023, where she can unite her enthusiasm for language, research, and transfer. She is keen to raise awareness for the multifaceted effects of language, its opportunities, and hidden treasures, all the while accompanying “Die Sprach-Checker”.

Rahaf Farag (EG) studied translation studies, linguistics, and cultural studies at the University of Mainz, Germany. Having earned her doctorate in intercultural communication in 2022, she started as a postdoc in the project “Data Collection and Language Documentation” at the Leibniz Institute for the German Language. She develops participatory formats to encourage citizens to contribute to linguistic research, thus creating new means for bilateral knowledge. To experiment with low-threshold opportunities for exchange and transfer, she has accompanied the Language Checkers from the start.

Heike Chan Hin (DE) studied German and biology at the University of Mainz, Germany, for the teaching profession at grammar schools. She brings her enthusiasm for education, science communication, and working with children and young people to the project “Die Sprach-Checker”. Her engagement is also reflected in her professional career, as an editor for pedagogical reference books at Beltz Verlag Weinheim, as a member of the educational team at the Climate Foundation for Citizens Sinsheim, and now as an Education and Outreach Officer at the Leibniz Institute for the German Language.

Theresa Schnedermann (DE) studied German linguistics and literature, philosophy, psychology, and pedagogy at Heidelberg University, Germany. She completed a doctoral dissertation on discourse linguistics. Since 2012, she has worked in public relations at the Leibniz Institute for the German Language. In the summer of 2022, she took up the position of communications officer in the emerging “Forum Deutsche Sprache”. As for the project “Die Sprach-Checker”, she is keen to work with the children and students to make their work visible and to inspire other children, young people, and supporters.

Sprach-Checker team at the IDS (DE) Alongside the initiators of the programme*, an enthusiastic team of scientists has been growing; team members draw on a wealth of experiences and languages, additionally to a rich expertise from various disciplines: linguistics, intercultural communication, translation studies, education, psychology, methodologies regarding data collection and curation, statistics, science communication, and public relations. The core team is constituted by Dr. Christine Möhrs*, Elena Schoppa-Briele*, Heike Chan Hin, Dr. Rahaf Farag, Dr. Janin Roessel, and Dr. Theresa Schnedermann.

Jury Statement

Statement by the jury of the European Union Prize for Citizen Science 2024: Mairéad Hurley (IE), Sofie Burgos-Thorsen (DK), Snežana Smederevac (RS), Fermín Serrano Sanz (ES), Luciana Marques (BR)

This initiative, based in Mannheim, Germany, is a commendable effort to explore and celebrate multilingualism, particularly within diverse communities often underrepresented in linguistic research. By engaging children and adolescents from varied backgrounds, the project aims to shift perceptions of multilingualism from deficit-oriented views to appreciation and empowerment. By involving citizen scientists in all stages of research, from question formulation to data collection and analysis, the project fosters a sense of ownership and pride in linguistic heritage among participants.

Let's go out with Pl@ntNet app!

Ivana Polackova (SK), Pierre Bonet (FR), Tereza NGO(CZ)

<https://calls.ars.electronica.art/2024/prix/winners/13237/>

Since 2016, in the Secret Life of the City project, this project has focused on increasing the environmental awareness of the public with the intention of highlighting biodiversity in cities through cooperation with more than 200 primary and secondary schools (also schools for students with special needs, mostly of Roma minority were included) from all over Slovakia and Czech Republic by connecting to information technologies and data collection.

The practical outputs of the project were creative adventurous quests created by pupils and students in their cities, which could be used as an educational tool for terrain biodiversity exploring and data collection. Many quests have also become a permanent part of the offer of local tourist information offices.

The project also enabled a connection between Slovak and Czech schools. They implemented their project activities in a mirror manner. The international cooperation in the field of this research was also supported by a 3-day long exploratory event in Slovakia, for 6 best working school teams which created the most inspirational public information campaigns about their local researchers.

The project contributes not only to the knowledge of the flora in the field, but by involving the public - it supports the rapid collection of data to an open GBIF platform for botanists from all over the world. Thanks to this project,

students' interest increased not only in biology and botany, but also in the study of scientific fields at universities.

In the ongoing cooperation with French botanists, developers of the Pl@ntNet and the State Nature Protection, they have also involved 20 high schools in the next Citizen Science project Let´s go out with Pl@ntNet! in 2020, right during the pandemic. Since Slovak secondary schools were closed for several months during the pandemic, the project was a very welcomed form of original, safe and modern way of education and at the same time also an inspiration of innovative distance education for other closed schools.

<https://huravon.sk/2021/06/28/online-kurz-hura-von-s-plntnetom-pre-ucitelov-lektorov/>

Credits

SK-NIC, a.s., (member of CentralNic GROUP PLC); www.sk-nic.sk – financial support

State Nature Protection – professional support

Biographies

Ivana Polackova (SK) studied environmental science at the Faculty of Natural Sciences of the Comenius University and has been working on various projects in Živica since 2000. Currently, it is the leadership of the organization and the outdoor learning platform Hura von. She has 2 active sons, with whom she and her husband are constantly on the move and especially outdoors.

Jury Statement

Statement by the jury of the European Union Prize for Citizen Science 2024: Mairéad Hurley (IE), Sofie Burgos-Thorsen (DK), Snežana Smederevac (RS), Fermín Serrano Sanz (ES), Luciana Marques (BR)

The Secret Life of the City project in Slovakia, ongoing since 2016, involves over 200 schools and 18,000 students in urban biodiversity protection using the Pl@ntNet app. Collaboration with botanists and scientists from France and Slovakia adds credibility and expertise to the project, encouraging young learners to become researchers and actively participate in data collection fosters a deep understanding of biodiversity. Implementing robust evaluation mechanisms and advocating for evidence-based policies aim to further amplify its influence on broader environmental initiatives.

Obstetric Coevolution: Coevolving obstetric practices to improve the childbirth experience

Irene Lapuente (ES), Anna Fosch Masllovet (ES), Dídac Roger i Homs (ES), La Mandarina de Newton (ES)

<https://calls.ars.electronica.art/2024/prix/winners/12586/>

Approximately one in six women experience postpartum depression, with adverse implications for both the woman and the newborn. Obstetric practices, such as induction, have also been associated with negative effects on perinatal care. Obstetric coevolution (OBCOE) seeks to delve into the relationship between obstetric practices and women's mental well-being to reduce postpartum depression. OBCOE aims to collaboratively evolve obstetric practices, thereby fostering a more positive birth experience. It contributes to SDG03, related to health and well-being, and SDG05 on gender equality.

OBCOE has been raised as a groundbreaking citizen science project led by La Mandarina de Newton and funded by IMPETUS. It started with a co-creation process involving 22 mothers and 15 birth professionals. Together, key areas for improvement in obstetric care were identified. An 80-question survey, answered by over 400 mothers, was also co-created to explore more scientific and quantitative questions. Five major challenges were identified: medicalisation, communication, fear before delivery, mental health beyond postpartum depression, like PTSD, and postpartum loneliness. Four proposals were put forward to deal with them: feedback sessions between mothers and professionals, better sexual and reproduction health education, a cross-cutting women's circle and dissemination of mother's needs. The co-created survey revealed a relationship between mental health and medicalisation during childbirth and the need to increase attention to postpartum.

OBCOE has created a growing community with a common goal of transforming obstetric practices. Placing women's will at the heart of childbirth is essential. With support from our citizen scientists and insights from over 400 responses, we stand ready to drive significant transformation. Advocating for policy shifts at the European level, our vision extends globally. Thanks to participatory science, we build trust and drive impactful transformation.

<https://www.obstetriccoevolution.eu/>

Credits

The project would like to thank all the volunteers and citizen scientists, especially the mothers and conscientious professionals, who co-created and inspired the project and the core team at la Mandarina de Newton. The project is a reality thanks to all of them.

We also would like to thank the associations and institutions that have trusted and supported the project.

OBCOE has been financially supported by the first and second editions of the IMPETUS grant.

Biographies

Irene Lapuente Aguilar (ES) obtained her bachelor's degree in physics (2002) at Barcelona University, her Postgraduate studies in Science Communication (2004) and Documentaries and reports for TV (2008) at the Pompeu Fabra University, and her Teaching Training (2004) at the Polytechnic University of Catalonia. She has designed co-creation processes in culture, art, science, health, and education since 2010. She is the founder and director of la Mandarina de Newton. Before creating her own company, she accumulated over ten years of experience in the scientific cultural field.

Anna Fosch Masllovet (ES) obtained her bachelor's in biomedical sciences (2015) and her Master's in Neurosciences (2017) at the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona. Anna earned her PhD in Health Science with the study of the central control of metabolism in 2022 (International University of Catalonia). She specialized in science communication in 2023 (Universitat de Vic). Currently, she is a researcher and project manager at La Mandarina de Newton, focused on the Obstetric Coevolution project.

Dídac Roger i Homs (ES) obtained his bachelor's degree in Audiovisual Communication (2001) at the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona. He has focused his career on the creation of informative, cultural and educational documentaries. One of his great achievements is the documentary Looking for the Mediterranean Flavour which won the prize for best European documentary about the Mediterranean Diet, produced within the framework of the SlowMed project. He is the founder and director of the production company Kineina Audiovisuals and a tight collaborator at la Mandarina de Newton since 2016.

La Mandarina de Newton (ES) is a cultural enterprise focused on science and technology. Our curious, innovative, and non-conformist spirit has led us to explore fields tangent to science, such as art, design, and audiovisual language. Our work explores the scientific method, design thinking and creative processes. We design tailor-made projects for each situation.

Research, ideation, production and execution of projects and training are a part of what we do. We have extensive experience in project management, in the fields of education, culture, health, innovation and scientific transfer.

Jury Statement

Statement by the jury of the European Union Prize for Citizen Science 2024: Mairéad Hurley (IE), Sofie Burgos-Thorsen (DK), Snežana Smederevac (RS), Fermín Serrano Sanz (ES), Luciana Marques (BR)

Obstetric Coevolution (OBCOE) is a pioneering citizen science initiative focused on enhancing women's mental well-being during childbirth. Through innovative methodologies and a transdisciplinary approach, OBCOE strives to revolutionise obstetric practices, guided by Open Science principles for transparency and collaboration. By tackling the critical issue of obstetric care and its impact on women's mental health, OBCOE engages professionals and mothers through extensive surveys, showcasing its profound social impact on combating postpartum depression and related mental health challenges.

OdourCollect and D-NOSES: Citizen Science to foster environmental governance and tackle odour pollution

Fundación Ibercivis (ES), Science For Change (ES)

<https://calls.ars.electronica.art/2024/prix/winners/12969/>

Human noses can detect trillions of smells, making them the best tool for odour detection. However, prolonged exposure to bad smells can turn this marvel into a nightmare. The WHO recognizes the impact of odour pollution on our health, accounting for 30% of environmental complaints overall. But odours are difficult to measure, and the lack of regulations translates into scarce data and unprotected citizens.

The D-NOSES project addressed this gap by developing a citizen science methodology to monitor odour pollution, validated through 10 case studies in Europe, Chile and Uganda, using OdourCollect for data collection. This collaborative work involved public administrations, industries, researchers and citizens, who worked closely to co-design solutions to reduce related impacts. The more than 13.800 odour observations collected by +2.630 citizens in 5 continents are openly available at <https://odourcollect.eu/map>.

Thanks to this huge amount of data, D-NOSES and OdourCollect have been able to inform public policies at different levels. At European level, D-NOSES

organised the event “Revisiting odour pollution in Europe” in the EU Parliament to call for a common regulatory framework and for the recognition of odour as an environmental pollutant. As a direct consequence, the CoR requested an amendment to the “EU Action Plan: Towards Zero Pollution for Air, Water and Soil” to incorporate citizen science to monitor odour pollution.

At a Spanish level, the validation of the methodology resulted in the publication of the Spanish standard UNE 77270:2023 “Building collaborative odour maps through citizen science”, the first of its kind.

OdourCollect continues to empower citizens to tackle odour pollution and encourages policymakers to take action, by providing reliable data to formulate evidence-informed public policies. Most importantly: they made visible the invisible, by putting all types of smells in the map, thanks to citizen science. OdourCollect has also developed scientific educational projects, workshops and activities at schools, libraries or Museums, creating artistic experiences focused on smells as a source of inspiration.

<https://odourcollect.eu/map>

<https://dnoses.eu/>

Credits

OdourCollect was originally funded in 2016 by the MyGeoss project (JRC). D-NOSES (2018-2021) received funding from the EU's H2020 research and innovation programme (Grant Agreement No. 789315). OdourCollect received funding from the Neotec programme (2022-2024), from the Spanish Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities. It also received the Prismas award in the category of singular project (Science Museums in Coruña) in 2021. The team acknowledges and expresses their gratitude to all citizens that actively participate reporting odour observations in OdourCollect throughout the years.

Biographies

Science For Change (ES) is a knowledge-based social enterprise that promotes collaborative research, evidence-informed public policies and quality science communication based in Barcelona. Currently, we are participating in more than 15 European, national and regional research and innovation projects, collaborating with more than 100 institutions throughout the world in more than 30 countries. Our interdisciplinary team is composed of more than 20 researchers, including the social sciences and humanities and the arts.

At Science For Change we address social, environmental and health challenges through citizen science, participatory strategies and co-creation. We facilitate collaborative research between different agents to co-design solutions to complex societal challenges that concern citizens and contribute

to evidence-informed public policies, pushing for social innovations and positive changes to improve society.

Fundación Ibercivis (ES) is a private non-profit Spanish foundation whose objectives are to carry out, promote and make citizen science visible. In order to achieve its objectives, and in collaboration with various scientific and social agents, the Ibercivis Foundation: - Carries out and promotes research in many different areas of scientific knowledge at local, national and international levels. - It provides technical support, dissemination and training so that anyone can participate in scientific research, according to their interests and always dynamic capabilities. We share resources and experience derived from our own citizen science activity. We conduct our own research by developing our own citizen science projects in which we theorise, prototype, model, evaluate impact, measure, develop technology and publish results. We promote the dissemination of the concept of "citizen science" through the development of the projects and through local, national and international events, exhibitions, publications, reports, awards, training and other activities.

Rosa Arias (ES) is a Chemical Engineer with extensive experience in odour pollution management and citizen science. She is the creator of the OdourCollect App and was the coordinator of the H2020 D-NOSES project (among others), which validated a new citizen methodology to monitor odour pollution that led to the creation of the Spanish technical standard UNE 77270:2023. To exploit the project results, she founded Science for Change, a knowledge-based social enterprise where innovative services based on citizen science, collaborative research, science communication, science to policy and co-creation for social innovation are developed. She is also a member of the Board of Directors of the European Citizen Science Association.

Jury Statement

Statement by the jury of the European Union Prize for Citizen Science 2024: Mairéad Hurley (IE), Sofie Burgos-Thorsen (DK), Snežana Smederevac (RS), Fermín Serrano Sanz (ES), Luciana Marques (BR)

D-NOSES addresses the overlooked issue of odour pollution in environmental policy. It engages 5,000 citizens from affected communities in 10 pilots across Spain, Greece, Portugal, Italy, UK, Germany Bulgaria, Chile and Uganda to monitor odour pollution with the OdourCollect app, centring citizens' perceptions of the problem and collecting open access data. Fostering collaboration between citizens, odour-emitting industries, environmental authorities, and academia, the project produces new scientific knowledge on the issue and proposes policy solutions at national and transnational levels within Europe, demonstrating the effectiveness of citizen science in addressing environmental challenges.

ParKli: Participatory climate research to develop local early warning systems for climate protection

ParKli Team (INT) ParKli Team (DE), Reutlingen University, Herman Hollerith Center (DE), open science for open societies – os4os (DE)

<https://calls.ars.electronica.art/2024/prix/winners/13366>

In ParKli, the impact and consequences of climate change on natural and living spaces are investigated. The three elements of co-design, co-production, and co-evaluation were used to interact with citizens in the research project. Every skill, age, and ability is welcome and a valuable contribution. Scientists and citizens work on an equal basis on different topics, e.g., water, biodiversity, soil, and urban area.

Interested parties can get involved at different levels and in various roles, from climate detectives who collect data via apps to citizen advisors who get more involved in the project, like identifying problems and needs and supporting the development of the Parkli toolbox.

Wherever possible, ParKli builds on proven open-source methods and integrates methods and data from projects such as iNaturalist, Greenspacehack, and EyeonWater. These projects have a worldwide active community, are open source, and give users access to their collected data. They are fully aligned with the project's objectives – only shared knowledge can make a real change.

In addition to that, IoT-sensors have been developed where APPs could not be used e.g. a buoy for monitoring the water quality of lakes and soil monitoring.

Citizen Science and Open Science aim to open up research by providing open access to data, publications, and other research products. ParKli sees itself as a driver of the research focus areas of Open Science and Citizen Science. The Parkli platform and toolbox includes best practice guidelines and methods for citizen science projects, the use of applications/APPs to collect, analyse and communicate data, and open access databases.

<https://parkli.de/>

Credits

The Parkli research project is funded by the Baden-Württemberg Foundation as part of the 'Innovations for adaptation to climate change' programme.

We would like to thank all the citizen scientists, (climate detectives and advisory boards) who have supported the Parkli journey as well as the developers and communities of iNaturalist, Greenspacehack and EyeOn Water.

Biographies

Reutlingen University, Herman Hollerith Center (HHZ) (DE) The HHZ is a teaching and research center and implements innovative study programs for modern computer science and business and applied research. The HHZ is integrated into the structures of Reutlingen University and the Faculty of Computer Science. Together with partners from science and industry, relevant issues in the field of business informatics are addressed in research and teaching.

open science for open societies - os4os is a non-profit organisation for the promotion of science, research and education (DE). To this end, we initiate projects in the areas of open science, citizen science, open data and open source. os4os focuses on the transfer of research results to civil society and develops corresponding methods and tools. A primary goal is the development and operation of the information portal

The consortium team working together on this project are:

Prof. Dr. Dieter Hertweck (DE) is a Professor for Service Science at the Faculty of Computer Science, Reutlingen University, and the project coordinator of Parkli.

Annette Kunz-Engesser (DE) is responsible for networking and activating citizen scientists. She is also the contact person for educational institutions such as schools and associations and develops new teaching formats.

Jan Fauser (DE) is working on data visualisation tools and data cleaning methods for the data collected by the apps and sensors used in Parkli.

Reiner Braun (DE) leads the scientific investigations and supports citizens in developing experiments, data collection, and the use of Parkli's toolbox.

Philip Regel (DE) is developing Parkli's core software elements and integrating them into cloud systems; he focuses on DevOps, IoT, and system architecture.

Tobias Kanaske (DE) is developing the Parkli open hardware sensors and integrating the sensor data into Parkli's data infrastructure.

Brigitte Braun (DE) who studied Man and Identity at the Design Academy Eindhoven, is the Communications and visibility coordinator developing the Parkli platform UI.

Sam S. Namin (DE) who studied animation in Babelsberg, is supporting with visuals like illustrations, animations, and videos.

Jury Statement

Statement by the jury of the European Union Prize for Citizen Science 2024: Mairéad Hurley (IE), Sofie Burgos-Thorsen (DK), Snežana Smederevac (RS), Fermín Serrano Sanz (ES), Luciana Marques (BR)

Parkli, a German initiative, employs co-design to engage citizens in documenting climate change impacts on biodiversity in natural and urban environments. Participating as 'climate detectives' or 'citizen advisors', the project has involved 1,500 citizens and school students in defining local ecological issues, collecting environmental data through mobile apps, and creating new technologies such as sensor buoys and data dashboards that close knowledge gaps in environmental informatics. The project develops innovative visualisation tools and breaks down data silos, creating interfaces between different citizen science projects to ensure that insights from local projects can be used across domains.

RadoNorm Citizen Science Incubator

Tanja Perko (SI), Meritxell Martell (ES), Warren John (DE)

<https://calls.ars.electronica.art/2024/prix/winners/10721/>

The European research project RadoNorm addresses the critical issue of radon, a dangerous indoor air pollutant causing over 21,000 annual lung cancer cases in EU member states. RadoNorm has set up a Citizen Science Incubator involving both, citizens and scientists from diverse scientific disciplines, from social sciences to dosimetry and medicine, to contribute to research related to testing and mitigation of radon in high-risk areas. The aim is to initiate many grassroots citizen science projects in radon risk areas around Europe.

The Incubator started with 4 pilot projects and is currently engaging nearly 800 citizen scientists across Europe. In France, citizens improved an on-line self-evaluation guide for radon diagnostic; in Ireland householders developed a Do-It-Yourself (DIY) mitigation toolkit; in Hungary, students invented a tool to measure various gaseous air pollutants in-doors and radon and in Norway citizens developed guidelines for DIY radon remediation. Transitioning from pilot to grassroots projects, the Incubator supports community-specific research questions in 6 countries. In Italy, citizens and students measure

radon levels, analyse data and create an interactive radon map. Polish high school students collect and analyse samples of soil, water and air, contributing to both education and research. In Portugal students run a monitoring campaign in an inland region of the country, poorly characterised in terms of radon measurements. In Slovakia, citizens, secondary construction school, faculty of civil engineering and an NGO investigate building mitigation strategies, while Slovenia conducts research on the effectiveness of different mitigation techniques and Spain targets both workplaces and homes for radon exposure reduction.

The RadoNorm Incubator continues to engage citizens and academics contributing to advancing scientific knowledge in radon-related health risks and ultimately lowering lung cancer cases.

<https://www.radonorm.eu/activities/radonorm-citizen-science/>
<https://eu-citizen.science/project/370>
<https://scistarter.org/radonorm>

Credits

This project has received funding from the Euratom research and training programme 2019–2020 RadoNorm under grant agreement No 900009. Our gratitude goes to the coordinators of the citizen science projects and citizens scientists, among others, C. Schieber (FR), V. Groma (HU), A. Dowdall (IE), Y. Tomkiv (NO), C. Antunes & N. Canha (PT), F. Bianchini, L. Grassi & C. Masetti (IT), A. Ďurecová & F. Ďurec (SK), K. König & D. Kocman (SI), A. Peiro, L. Quindós & F. Sanz (ES) and D. Aksamit (PL). Sincere thanks to M. A. Hoedoafia from SCK CEN (BE) for her assistance in the citizen science incubator.

Biographies

Tanja Perko (SI/BE), senior researcher at SCK CEN, PhD in Social sciences (University of Antwerp), MSc in political studies and Bachelor's in journalism (University of Ljubljana). She coordinated several European projects in the field of communication and radiological risk management. Currently, she is coordinating social science research in the RadoNorm project (2020-2025). She is vice-chair of the SHARE platform. Her areas of expertise include risk communication and perception, health communication, mass media, stakeholder involvement and participation, societal aspects of emergency management and public opinion.

Meritxell Martell (ES), founder and director of Merience, a consultancy company focused on environmental risk governance; PhD in Environmental Sciences from the University of East Anglia (UEA, Norwich, United Kingdom). She has over 20 years of experience as an international consultant, working for different international organisations. She is currently leading the task on RadoNorm Citizen Science Incubator. She is the secretary of the SHARE platform on Social Sciences and Humanities in Ionising Radiation Research

Warren John (DE), scientific officer at the Federal Office for Radiation Protection (BfS) in Germany. He obtained his PhD in biochemistry, and then entered the field of radioecology, investigating migration of radionuclides in soil and plants. He is currently the RadoNorm project coordinator.

Jury Statement

Statement by the jury of the European Union Prize for Citizen Science 2024: Mairéad Hurley (IE), Sofie Burgos-Thorsen (DK), Snežana Smederevac (RS), Fermín Serrano Sanz (ES), Luciana Marques (BR)

The H2020 project RadoNorm addresses radon, a significant indoor air pollutant causing over 21,000 lung cancer cases annually in the EU. With approximately 600 citizens and 57 research organisations involved, it pioneers a Citizen Science Incubator to tackle radon risks. With citizen science projects across Italy, Poland, Portugal, Slovakia, Slovenia, and Spain, RadoNorm employs diverse approaches to improve radon measurements and mitigation, yielding innovative dosimeters, mitigation techniques and heightened awareness. The collaboration brilliantly bridges research, community engagement, and advocacy, contributing to long-term policy objectives aiming to reduce lung cancer cases.

SEED LIBRARY

Saša Vidmar (SI), Ana Kosič (SI), Irena Škvarč (SI), France Bevk Public Library (SI)

<https://calls.ars.electronica.art/2024/prix/winners/12946>

France Bevk Public Library (FBPL) is located in a town surrounded by rural areas, which are mainly cultivated by amateur gardeners. Some buy seeds from large seed stores, while others use seeds passed down to their families through generations. Organised seed exchanges have also been taking place in the local community. Therefore, the Seed Library (SL) was a logical extension of activities in our environment. For the needs of the SL, they started developing an application in collaboration with an external contractor. The application is intuitive and very easy to use, which allows users to use it independently. This application enables, in addition to seed borrowing, traceability of individual seeds and provides general descriptions. Users can also make notes related to seed cultivation, plants, and their uses. The SL operates on the principle of seed circulation. Users can donate home-grown, organically harvested seeds to the SL, which are then available to other users. They can also borrow seeds, plant them at home, grow plants, harvest the seeds, and return a portion of them to the SL. In addition to seed circulation, the SL engages local communities with various activities (workshops, lectures,

gardening club). Other public libraries in Slovenia quickly became interested in the SL initiative. Today, there are 22 SL coordinated by FBPL in Slovenian public libraries. The main goal of the SL is to raise awareness in the community about the importance of biodiversity, self-sufficiency, organic food production and sustainability. In this way, agronomic experts can reach a larger number of residents with their messages, while also having access to the seed collection being built by individuals. This provides experts with data on plants circulating among people, along with all associated information that people entered into the database. The catalogue of seeds in the SL is public and accessible through the websites of participating public libraries.

<https://www.gkfb.si/za-uporabnike/knjiznica-semen>

<https://www.gkfb.si/en/>

Credits

Ekosplet is a company that has been with us since the very beginning. Together, we have developed an application that enables borrowing, returning, and tracking of seeds. They take care that everything is running smoothly and are involved in the app's further development.

Rosana Vrh Makarovič is a university graduate engineer in agriculture. Her exceptional professional support regarding the agricultural part of the Seed Library was vital. Her support varied from naming and classifying plants into the right groups to conducting several lectures and workshops for various target user groups.

Biographies

Saša Vidmar (SI) graduated in Library and Information Science and has been working at the France Bevk Public Library Nova Gorica for more than 20 years. She is a coordinator of regional tasks and Head of Library development department. She is a co-creator of the "Rastem z e-viri" (Growing with e-resources project - for youngsters) and the head of the Mojstrovalnica (makespace) and Seed library projects, as well as a member of several working groups. She is also the president of the Promotion and Marketing Section (Slovenian Library Association).

Ana Kosič (SI) graduated in Library and Information Science and is a librarian in France Bevk Public Library Nova Gorica. She works in the non-fiction department, looks after the Seed Library, manages the library's social media

accounts and conducts information literacy project "Rastem z e-viri" at schools in Goriška region.

Irena Škvarč (SI) graduated in library science and history education. She has been active in the professional library environment since 1994. Since 2001, she has been employed at the France Bevk Public Library, where she led the Department for Special Tasks of the regional library, since 2013 she has been the director of the library. She participated in the establishment of the online portal of Slovenian public libraries, Dobreknjige.si. She actively participates in the Executive Board of the Association of Public Libraries and the Executive Board of the Slovenian Library Association. Since 2013, she has been the president of the Primorska and Notranjska Librarians' Association.

Jury Statement

Statement by the jury of the European Union Prize for Citizen Science 2024: Mairéad Hurley (IE), Sofie Burgos-Thorsen (DK), Snežana Smederevac (RS), Fermín Serrano Sanz (ES), Luciana Marques (BR)

Seed Library addresses the negative impacts of the agricultural industry on native ecology and biodiversity. With seed libraries in 20 public libraries across Slovenia, the project aims to preserve the biodiversity of local indigenous plants through free seed circulation, using a digital tool to record the lending of seeds, ensure their traceability and classification, and collect agronomic data about where individual plants grow and thrive. Through education activities, Seed Library creates knowledge transfer from experienced gardeners to beginners, reinforcing community solidarity, encouraging an exchange of sustainable farming practices, and fostering the conservation of home-grown seeds.

Sicily's Indigenous Cyber Tracker

Collettivo Rewild Sicily (IT), CyberTracker Italia (IT), Sicily Environment Fund (IT), Astrid Natura (IT)

<https://calls.ars.electronica.art/2024/prix/winners/13680/>

In recent years, indigenous knowledge has become a powerful tool for nature conservation, rewilding, and habitat restoration. However, traditional "top-down" conservation methods often exclude local communities, leading to unmet conservation goals. Recognising the vital role of indigenous knowledge and people, termed by UNEP as the "unsung heroes of conservation," is essential.

Europe presents a unique context, shaped by millennia of cultivation, infrastructure development, and wildlife depletion. Sicily, the Mediterranean's largest island, faces "cultural desertification." The key question here is: what constitutes indigenous knowledge, and who are its custodians?

This project identifies Sicily's local custodians: hunters, shepherds, and forestry workers. These individuals, deeply connected to the land and its traditions, are often marginalised but hold valuable ecological knowledge crucial for conservation.

They integrate these "Sicily's Indigenous CyberTrackers" by tracking wildlife, signs of fire, and human activity, feeding this data into the CyberTracker app. This approach gathers essential data and bridges the gap between custodians and conservation efforts.

The impact is twofold. First, the collected data creates a robust database to inform and influence policy. Second, the initiated dialogue forms a cohesive community. So far, this project has engaged local custodians in field activities, developed a customised CyberTracker app, co-created educational materials, and a short documentary. An advocacy workshop was hosted to integrate local ecological knowledge into broader land management policies.

Looking ahead, they plan to expand their community, conduct more site visits across Sicily, and explore new business models combining the expertise of nature guides with local hunters and shepherds. By continuing to collect data and enrich their database, and aim to professionalise tracking and valorise indigenous knowledge, making it a cornerstone of effective conservation efforts.

<https://collettivorewildsicily.com/>

Credits

IMPETUS has supported this project. IMPETUS is funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme.

The project joint efforts together with another one "Rewilding Guide Training" financed by Sicily Environment Fund.

Photography credits by Mathia Coco.

Trainers: Georg Messerer (DE) and Toni Romani (IT)

all the participants to the infield training and workshop (IT)

Biographies

Collettivo Rewild Sicily (IT) is a local non-profit dedicated to rewilding actions in Sicily co-founded by Hanna Rasper, Luisa Sausa, Salvatore Bondì and Enrico Guzzo.

Collettivo Rewild Sicily was born from a specific need: to make Sicily a greener, wilder, and a more conscious place.

We work on small projects that are meant to be practical, easily repeatable and regenerate small local communities and their love for the land they live in. We act to build a better world, simple and in small steps. We think globally and act locally, on this magical island where every corner is a wonder.

We do this mainly by trying to decrease the human-wildlife conflict. Our tools are agroforestry, anti-wildfire actions, regenerative grazing, and rewilding.

Jury Statement

Statement by the jury of the European Union Prize for Citizen Science 2024: Mairéad Hurley (IE), Sofie Burgos-Thorsen (DK), Snežana Smederevac (RS), Fermín Serrano Sanz (ES), Luciana Marques (BR)

Exploring the biodiversity crisis, this project addresses Sicily's potential for rewilding by creating an open, comprehensive wildlife database to stimulate a long-term 'pro-rewilding' culture among decision-makers in the region. Leveraging the CyberTracker tool, the project foregrounds otherwise marginalised indigenous knowledge by engaging hunters, shepherds, forestry services, and nature guides in collecting data on wildlife and land management. Through workshops, the project puts such local knowledge into dialogue with researchers, NGOs, and decision-makers, advocating for policy changes, establishing the Collettivo Rewild Sicily, and promoting inclusive, community-driven rewilding efforts in Sicily.

Social inclusion and participation of Deaf and Hard of Hearing adults in Citizen Science for Climate Change (CitSci4All)

Katerina Zourou (GR)

<https://calls.ars.electronica.art/2024/prix/winners/13217/>

To achieve its goals, the project developed innovative accessible materials for deaf and hard of hearing (DHH) trainers and adults to facilitate their active involvement in citizen science for climate change.

CitSci4All expanded its knowledge on the inclusion of DHH citizens in research, by offering a robust framework based on citizen science principles. Thus, the project delivered a series of educational materials, aimed to introduce DHH adults to citizen science, and its tools. CitSci4All aimed also at influencing policy, by heightening awareness of the social value of Citizen Science (CS) within disadvantaged communities in Europe. Through the implementation of citizen science mini-projects by DHH communities of the partner countries, participants' developed, reflected and shared their ideas and insights with regards to public participation in science.

CitSci4All placed a strong emphasis on co-creative learning, with stakeholders from diverse backgrounds, spanning various fields, from education to training and science. Moreover, CitSci4All was designed on the premise of diversity and collaboration to foster inclusion of DHH citizens in citizen science projects and initiatives for climate advocacy and climate awareness. Digital technology and tools were a key instrument of communication but also of propagation of knowledge and expertise from partners to DHH participants. The CitSci4All Online Citizen Science Toolkit (<https://citsci4all.eu/citizen-science-toolkit/>) is an innovative resource, designed to be accessible and DHH-friendly. The online toolkit is open access for all DHH citizens to use, while it is available in 4 EU languages, namely French, Italian, Greek and Cypriot. Additionally, CitSci4All developed a bonus educational material that fosters creativity and citizen science skills of DHH citizens; this material takes the form of a card game available open access to all interested parties (<https://citsci4all.eu/bonus-material/>).

<https://citsci4all.eu/>

Credits

We would like to thank and acknowledge the meaningful work and collaboration of all Deaf and Hard-of-Hearing (DHH) adults who participated in project activities in the 4 project countries, from Greece and Cyprus to Italy and France. We would also like to thank the DHH educators and Sign Language interpreters who facilitated our engagement with the DHH communities throughout the project.

Biographies

Katerina Zourou (GR) is a recognised researcher in the area of technology-enhanced education, focusing on open and social learning in education. She has produced one scholar book (Palgrave/ MacMillan), three journal special issues and more than 30 peer reviewed papers at international journals and conference proceedings. She is regularly invited to give talks or to participate in expert panels. Katerina is the Managing Director of [Web2Learn](#), a R&D

company in Thessaloniki, Greece, established in 2014. Web2Learn is a partner in more than 20 transnational EU-funded projects.

Christophe Kedzia (FR) is Director of the [IRSAM](#) organisation. IRSAM supports people with disabilities, mainly those with sensory impairments, in specialised (sheltered) workspaces, in mainstream settings, as well as, in learning and training centers.

Enrico Dolza (IT) has a PhD in Special Education at University of Torino and he has extensive experience in the field of education and training, mainly related with disability studies and politics. He is executive Director at the [Turin Institute for the Deaf](#), he is contract professor of Special Education at the University of Torino. Enrico has over 10 years experience in developing and managing EU projects and he has been involved in over 16 EU funded projects.

Yiota Mourettou (CY) is the Head of Research and Development at [Citizens In Power](#) (CIP). Yiota is coordinating the projects of CIP. Yiota has obtained a diploma in Applied Mathematics and Physics by the National Technical University of Athens. She has studied acting at the prestigious Drama School of Greek Art Theatre-KarolosKoun in Greece, whilst she has acquired a Master Degree (MSc) in Media and Communications by the London School of Economics (LSE).

Thanos Loules (GR) is working in the administrative department of IT at [IASIS](#). He has studied as a computer network applications technician and office automation, and he is active in the technical field. Also, he has participated in training of network and computer installations. In addition, he has participated in volunteer actions. His key competences are i) adjustable, ii) hardworking, iii) methodic in problem solving.

Jury Statement

Statement by the jury of the European Union Prize for Citizen Science 2024: Mairéad Hurley (IE), Sofie Burgos-Thorsen (DK), Snežana Smederevac (RS), Fermín Serrano Sanz (ES), Luciana Marques (BR)

CitSci4All is an initiative that empowers Deaf and Hard of Hearing (DHH) people to participate in citizen science efforts actively focused on climate change. Through workshops, materials, and community engagement efforts, the project improves scientific understanding and promotes inclusivity, diversity, and meaningful contributions to the DHH community and the wider scientific community.

The Home River Bioblitz

Jens Benöhr Riveros (CL), Vera Knook (NL), Carlos Velazco (MX), Enya Roseli (MX), Jelena Belojević (ME)

<https://calls.ars.electronica.art/2024/prix/winners/13328/>

The Home River Bioblitz is a global citizen science initiative that aims to document and protect the richness of river ecosystems. Originating during the COVID-19 pandemic, this grassroots project emerged as a citizen-led effort to empower local communities to understand, appreciate, and conserve their nearby rivers and water bodies. As 2024 marks its fifth year, the project has cultivated a worldwide river community, fostering connections among rivers, diverse cultures, and countries through digital events and social networks.

During the Home River Bioblitz, the project has gone out to explore their local rivers together with peers, friends and family, thereby enlarging local networks of people that care about rivers. The project identifies the observed species with help of the global iNaturalist community. During an online recap session, they chat about the day with various specialists, zooming into some remarkable observations as well as discussing new ways to relate to this local river wildlife. The main spirit of the event is to celebrate and learn about rivers and their biodiversity as integral components of our society.

<https://www.homeriverbioblitz.org/>
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3GJiR-BQ5YA>

Biographies

Jens Benöhr (CL) is a Chilean-German anthropologist, ecologist and kayaker dedicated to environmental education and science communication. Benöhr has spent the last years working in various environmental groups, including the collective Bestias del Sur Salvaje, a group of athletes who seek to link outdoor sports with socio-environmental activism, and the River Collective, a Europe based NGO that works in river conservation and science education in Eastern European countries.

Vera Knook (NL) is a river lover from the Netherlands, who lives in Peru. Rivers have shaped her life since she started kayaking at 14 years old. In 2017, Vera graduated as a hydraulic engineer, but soon got involved in the protection of rivers. In 2019 Knook found a team to organise the first Students for Rivers Camp. This resulted in the foundation of the River Collective. Vera loves creating opportunities with this community, as well as being a seasonal raft guide on the Marañón River (Perú).

Carlos Velazco (MX) is a Mexican biologist with graduate studies, trained as a botanist but turned into a Naturalist and citizen science advocate; he has devoted most of his professional life since 2006 to documenting biodiversity through photography, especially with neglected species such as endemic wildflowers and invertebrates, since 2013 he is one of the top users on iNaturalist, a world-leading platform to document biodiversity. He also works to educate a wide range of audiences in biodiversity topics providing

educational talks and seminars and publishing articles both scientific and informal, he is currently working as an independent professional.

Enya Roseli Enriquez Brambila (MX) is an ecohydrologist, focusing on sustainable water resource management and social participation. Enya graduated as BSc in Natural Resources, with a Master's in Watershed Management, and an ongoing Hydroinformatics PhD at IHE, Netherlands. Enya coordinates an ONG in her region named "Vigilando Rios y Arroyos" where she promotes conservative actions towards local rivers. Her work integrates citizen science and nature research with digital platforms to enhance environmental education and engagement.

Jelena Belojević (ME) is an Ornithologist, Behavioural and Conservation Biologist originating from Montenegro. Belojević spent the last five years researching behaviour and conservation of some of the most endangered shorebird populations in Europe, ruffs and southern dunlins in both Max Planck Institute for Biological Intelligence in Germany, and University of Oulu in Finland. Her goal is to connect basic research with conservation and inform currently ongoing management practices to improve the conditions of breeding and migratory habitats for shorebirds.

Jury Statement

Statement by the jury of the European Union Prize for Citizen Science 2024: Mairéad Hurley (IE), Sofie Burgos-Thorsen (DK), Snežana Smederevac (RS), Fermín Serrano Sanz (ES), Luciana Marques (BR)

The Home River Bioblitz empowers communities to become stewards of their local rivers. By engaging in citizen science activities such as biodiversity documentation and data analysis, participants contribute to scientific research and gain a deeper understanding of the importance of river conservation. The project is building a network of individuals and organisations dedicated to protecting and preserving the river ecosystems for future generations.

The Russian airstrike on the Mariupol Drama Theatre

The Center for Spatial Technologies (UA)

<https://calls.ars.electronica.art/2024/prix/winners/13735/>

The destruction and subsequent occupation of Mariupol by the Russian Armed Forces have fragmented its communities, leaving most survivors

dispersed across different regions of Ukraine, other parts of Europe, and beyond reconstruction. This project looks at the bombing of the Mariupol Drama Theatre as an emblem of Russia's strategies of terror. Their aim is to assemble the voices of members of the Mariupol Theater diaspora within a digital project of reconstruction.

The CST team has collected and analysed thousands of social media posts, photographs, and videos in addition to recording over one hundred hours of interviews with witnesses. With no access to the site and with the systematic destruction of both physical and digital evidence, these recollections constitute an essential historical document. The project used the model as a backdrop for situated testimonies and later to locate visual materials documenting the theater during the siege and after its occupation.

Their team identified sixty eyewitnesses of the events, out of which twenty-seven agreed to talk to us on record. They invited ten witnesses to participate in further interview sessions using the "situated testimony" technique developed by our partnering organization, Forensic Architecture. This collaborative reconstruction process allowed survivors to 'walk' through the virtual space and model different aspects of the building as they remembered it. This process facilitated recollection and helped our team to fill in missing details in the digital models. As each witness recalled their part in this complex event, the model became an increasingly rich assemblage of collective memory.

<https://theater.spatialtech.info/en>

Credits

This study is conducted by the Center for Spatial Technologies (CST) in collaboration with Forensis & Forensic Architecture. We were working with numerous external contributors to make this project happen.

Core CST team: Maksym Rokmaniko, Mykola Holovko, Daryna Vilkhova, Ksenia Rybak, Valeria Prorizna, Andrii Onyshchenko, Oksana Hrabchak, Sasha Zakrevska, Natasha Pereverzina, Herman Mitish, Orest Yaremchuk.

The Mariupol Theater Project is a long-term endeavour, realised through stages with the support of various financial contributions. The initial research phase, focused on gathering detailed information about the tragedy and planning subsequent activities, was funded by the Porticus Foundation. This foundational work, done in collaboration with Forensic Architecture / Forensis, set the groundwork for a comprehensive approach to documenting and analysing the events.

Following this, the recording of 12 interviews in the "situational testimony" format, conducted in Kyiv and Berlin, was supported by the ISAR Ednannia Foundation. The International Renaissance Foundation then contributed to

the processing and preparation of these interviews for publication. In November 2023, the House of Europe program provided funds for public events in Berlin and Kyiv, aiming to share our research findings with a broader audience.

Detailed List of Credits and Contributions
<https://theater.spatialtech.info/en/credits>

Biographies

The Center for Spatial Technologies (CST) is a transdisciplinary research group based in Kyiv and Berlin, at the intersection of architecture, the social sciences, investigative and artistic practices. Focused on the multifaceted study of urban environments across time, CST collaborates with a diverse array of cultural, academic, and human rights organizations to render visible various societal important issues, and their spatial implications. CST's works are featured on leading global platforms, including The New York Times, the Venice Biennale, and President Volodymyr Zelensky's social media.

Jury Statement

Statement by the jury of the European Union Prize for Citizen Science 2024: Mairéad Hurley (IE), Sofie Burgos-Thorsen (DK), Snežana Smederevac (RS), Fermín Serrano Sanz (ES), Luciana Marques (BR)

The Russian airstrike on the Mariupol Drama Theatre merges art, technology, and activism to honour the resilience of the Mariupol community post-tragedy. Led by the Center for Spatial Technologies, it redefines documentation through multimedia installations and witness testimonies, inviting audiences to engage empathetically. With citizen engagement at its core, this initiative is a testament to the power of citizen science in amplifying marginalised voices and challenging historical narratives.

The State of Our Trails (SoOT) Report: understanding and responding to single- use pollution (SUP) in recreational trail ecosystems through citizen science

<https://calls.ars.electronica.art/2024/prix/winners/12628/>

Intro

Up to 23 times more plastic pollution escapes into terrestrial ecosystems than oceans.

The SoOT Report aims to replicate the 'Blue Planet' effect for terrestrial ecosystems. Their aim is to understand the causes, prevalence, composition and impacts of SUP on recreational trails and their users.

Since July 2020, their citizen scientists have removed and recorded over 230,000 items of SUP and submitted over 700 data sets. Here's what they found.

Causes

SoOT conducted a meta-analysis to understand 'littering behaviour'. Initial themes that have emerged include: disconnection, disgust, control (or lack thereof), and social proof.

Prevalence

To establish SUP prevalence the project carried out 'Trash Counts'. Citizen scientists counted SUP items on 5,030kms of trails at 350 locations. There was an average of 42 items per km; a trail user may encounter an item of SUP every 24m.

Composition

To establish SUP composition they carried out 'Trash Surveys'. 81% of all items encountered on trails were single use products. 10% of items wouldn't exist if we had a Deposit Return Scheme.

Impact

To investigate ecological impact, SoOT established monitoring sites in 6 forest locations, over 9 months, with 790 hours of fieldwork and analysis.

They estimate that 1,891 acres of flora is being choked by SUP in the UK. 32% of submissions reported animal interaction and 21% reported animal death.

Qualitative data suggests that SUP negatively impacts individuals' experiences of nature. But trail cleans affect volunteers positively: 90% reported increased pride and felt more connected to nature, and 99% would take part again.

Thanks and next steps

This research was made possible thanks to 4,250 citizen scientists and our academic and corporate partners. The SoOT report launch reached 208,517 people, and over 3,000 people have visited its webpage. In aligning our work with the Global Plastic Treaty and the United Nations' SDGs this lays the ground for further research across Europe.

<https://www.trashfreetrails.org/>
https://www.trashfreetrails.org/_files/ugd/e60ede_7b277a11844f411bb4822304860e9518.pdf

Credits

Contributing Consultants

Tom Hill (GB) Copywriting

Rebecca Kaye (GB) Data visualisation

Dr Martyn Kurr (GB) Academic oversight

Dr Em Pope (GB) Nature Connection oversight

Supporting Partners

Bosch eBike Systems

The North Face & The European Outdoor Conservation Association (EOCA)

Trek Bikes UK

komoot

Red Bull

Orbea

Bangor University

Biographies

Dom Ferris (UK) is the founder and CEO of Trash Free Trails. As a lifelong mountain biker working at Surfers Against Sewage (SAS), Dom was struck by the deafening silence on the issue of single-use pollution on trial ecosystems, versus the growing concern for ocean plastic pollution. In 2017 he started an Instagram account, and from there Trash Free Trails blossomed into the international community of runners, riders and roamers seeking to protect what they love, it is today.

Trash Free Trails HQ (UK)

We are a 'smallnormous' organisation, who aim to catalyse enormously positive impact by creating projects that inspire, inform and equip people to take action.

As such, we don't have a HQ. What we do have is a group of people who combine their love for our wild places with perfectly aligned academic qualifications. Such as Rich, with an MSc in Psychology of Mental Health from The University of Edinburgh. And Rach, with an MSc in Movement, Mind & Ecology from Schumacher College. Or PJ, a Bangor University work placement student, who leads our Citizen Science training programme.

Jury Statement

Statement by the jury of the European Union Prize for Citizen Science 2024: Mairéad Hurley (IE), Sofie Burgos-Thorsen (DK), Snežana Smederevac (RS), Fermín Serrano Sanz (ES), Luciana Marques (BR)

The Sustainable Trails Initiative focuses on reducing single-use pollution (SUP) on UK recreational trails. Its impact lies in comprehensive research, utilising over 700 datasets and engaging 4,250 citizen scientists. The initiative's SoOT Report delves into SUP causes, prevalence, composition, and impacts, shedding light on a critical environmental issue. This initiative empowers community involvement and aligns efforts with global plastic treaties. The project's tangible impact includes the removal of over 200,000 SUP items and increased nature connection among participants.

Youth partnership in suicide prevention research: fostering authenticity, collaboration and empowerment.

Maria Michail (GR), Niyah Campbell (GB), Rowmell Hunter (GB), Zaynab Sohawon (GB), Jamie Morgan (GB), Beckye Williams (GB), Kalen Reid (GB)

<https://calls.ars.electronica.art/2024/prix/winners/11085/>

Suicide is a leading cause of death among young people aged 15 to 29 globally. However, young people with lived experience of self-harm or suicidal behaviour are rarely involved in the design of research that affects them due to concerns about them being 'too vulnerable' to influence such research. We believe that shutting youth experts by experience out of involvement perpetuates the historical power differentials in mental health research, excluding those whose voices should be listened to.

This project set out to challenge how we conduct research into suicide prevention by placing young people as experts by experience at the forefront of research design, delivery and implementation.

The Institute for Mental Health Youth Advisory Group (YAG) consists of 12 young people aged between 18 and 25 with lived experience of mental ill-health. This group was formed to provide an avenue through which young experts by experience could shape our research in a way that fosters collaboration and empowerment.

YAG members set the agenda for our research program by leading priority setting workshops. YAG members meaningfully contributed to the design of research and co-produced a novel, evidence-based resource, #MyGPguide, offering advice and support to young people when seeking help through primary care services for self-harm or suicidal experiences. YAG members led on dissemination activities to promote #MyGPguide including a Twitter chat, generating 16.2 million impressions, and co-authoring an open-access, academic article reflecting on the importance of youth partnership in improving the quality of suicide research.

#MyGPguide has now been adopted by a range of UK professional groups including safeguarding boards in Wales and health authorities in Derbyshire which feature #MyGPguide on their website as a critical resource for supporting the emotional health and wellbeing of young people. #MyGPguide has reached circa 300 GP practices in the West Midlands.

<https://www.birmingham.ac.uk/research/mental-health/youth-advisory-group>

<https://www.birmingham.ac.uk/research/mental-health/gp-guide-for-young-people>

Credits

School of Psychology, University of Birmingham

The Institute of Advanced Studies, University of Birmingham

Impact Fund, College of Life and Environmental Sciences, University of Birmingham

Biographies

Dr Maria Michail (GR) is an Associate Professor and leads the suicide and self-harm research group at the Institute for Mental Health, University of Birmingham. Her work focuses on understanding the processes that underlie self-harm and suicidal behaviour in young people with multiple vulnerabilities; and, using this knowledge to develop evidence-based interventions and policies to improve young people's care and outcomes. Maria has an extensive track record in citizen science and youth engagement throughout her academic work.

Niyah Campbell (UK) is the Senior Patient and Public Involvement and Engagement Lead for the School of Psychology, University of Birmingham. His work has been instrumental in developing practices surrounding involvement of experts by experience in research within the Institute for Mental Health, most notably through setting up and sustaining engagement with the IMH YAG. Campbell's influence extends to with other areas with academia, with notable examples being engagement with the National Centre for Co-ordinating Public Engagement and the Wellcome Trust.

Rowmell Hunter (UK) I am part of the Youth Advisory Group at the Institute of Mental Health, University of Birmingham, UK. I am passionate about mental health and empowering young adults because we live in a world where it is hard to speak out especially being from an ethnic background. I also work as a Christian theatre actor that make shows about social issues that impact young adults and how we can tackle it. This is important to me as people don't get a chance to share their message or make their stamp in the world because they don't feel heard or appreciated.

Zaynab Sohawon (UK) I am ZeZe, a 22-year-old young person from the Youth Advisory Group at the Institute for Mental Health. I have lived experience of autism and psychosis. I was sectioned for 4 years as a teen. As a result of working with the Youth Advisory Group, I have co-authored papers, become a peer researcher, and engaged in public speaking events. I am now CEO of my own mental health charity that I have set up and have raised just over £80k. YAG has been transformative and was the catalyst I needed to change my life and the world around me.

Jamie Morgan (UK) is a youth mental health advocate who has made significant contributions to the field of mental health science. Notable contributions as an IMH YAG member include co-presenting #MyGPguide at the IAYMH Conference 2022, Copenhagen, providing a keynote speech on involving young experts by experience in mental health research at the PsyYoung Conference 2023, Geneva and co-authoring an academic article (2023) journal on youth partnership in suicide prevention research where he reflected on his experience of being involved in the design of #MyGPguide. Jamie works as Lived Experience Advisor within the Wellcome Trust's Mental Health Team.

Becky Williams (UK) recently progressed from the role of IMH YAG member to Youth Involvement Officer for the Institute for Mental Health, University of Birmingham. Having transitioned into a professional post, her role is to provide lead support on youth involvement practices within the IMH. In her time as a YAG member, Williams was directly involved in the design of #MyGPguide notable activities she was involved in co-leading teaching sessions for Medical Students about the importance of taking a person-centered approach to supporting young people with mental health challenges.

Kalen Reid (UK) has a professional background in working with children and young people in a variety of contexts, including in research. They lead a Youth

Violence Intervention team at a Major Trauma Centre where their main responsibility is to manage youth workers who specialise in supporting those who have experienced serious youth violence and other forms of trauma. Kalen is a passionate supporter of participatory and liberatory practices in all spheres of their work and has worked directly with IMH professionals to co-author and disseminate research on self-harm in eating disorders.

Jury Statement

Statement by the jury of the European Union Prize for Citizen Science 2024: Mairéad Hurley (IE), Sofie Burgos-Thorsen (DK), Snežana Smederevac (RS), Fermín Serrano Sanz (ES), Luciana Marques (BR)

This UK-based project pioneers youth involvement in suicide prevention research, showcasing how young people with lived mental health experiences become leaders in shaping clinical practice. The Institute for Mental Health Youth Advisory Group (YAG) collaborates with researchers, co-designing resources like #MyGPguide, which offers vital support to at-risk youth seeking help through their GP. YAG members disseminate resources widely, influencing policy and empowering peers. With 12 engaged citizens, this initiative exemplifies meaningful youth engagement in driving mental health advocacy and systemic change.

10. Index Images

- **Image 1.** The jury of the European Union Prize for Citizen Science 2024 (L-R) – Fermín Serrano Sanz (ES), Snežana Smederevac (RS), Sofie Burgos-Thorsen (DK), Luciana Marques (BR), Mairéad Hurley (IE) Credit: Florian Voggeneder
Pag. 12
- **Image2.**
Common_bean_six_different_colored_lines_on_bean@Elisa_Bellucci_I
NCREASE_consortium.jpg | Credits:
@Elisa_Bellucci_INCREASE_consortium
Pag. 20
- **Image3.** INCREASE_clip1_screenshot3@INCREASE_consortium.png |
Credits: @INCREASE_consortium
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- **Image4.** 1_Spring_Water@GiuseppeLupinacci.jpg | Credits: Giuseppe
Lupinacci
Pag. 26
- **Image 5.** The Restart Project. Credit: The Restart Project / Mark Phillips
Pag.30